

H2020 Work Programme

D 3.3 - Report on detailed budget for running and maintaining the six BBEC and financial plan

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Acronyms and abbreviations

BBEC	Biobased Education Centre
EC	European Commission
GP	General Public
PM	Policy Makers
WP	Work Package

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Executive summary

WP3 provides detailed plans for implementation of the BBEC covering vocational, academic, and life-long learning, in a coordinated and consistent form. The specific objective of Task 3.3, which is reported in this deliverable is to provide an economic analysis of the feasibility of the centres, including a detailed screening of potential funding sources and models.

The work has been conducted in phases. A first indicative work on the budget and finances was discussed in Seville in January 2023, the methodological templates adopted and gathered during the spring of 2023. The work has been challenged by the very different preconditions and needs in each region, resulting in quite different economic calculations.

The type of costs includes costs for capacity building and costs for operating the centres. Costs for capacity building vary from € 15.000 to € 245.000 while operational costs vary from € 757.286 to € 1.852.375,

All inputs from the six BBECs have been aligned as much as possible, but still, the resulting balances of the economic performances varies from negative to rather positive. Among other facts, this reflects the varying optimism and the opportunities for external funding in each case, and not necessarily the degree on economic sustainability. However, the parallel calculations may give food for thoughts on the difficulty in finding a competitive business model and inspire all six BBECs for and improved update on the calculations, before applying for funds and establishing the BBECs.

Concerning external funding opportunities, there are numerous local and national opportunities to receive support for an initial phase of BBEC establishment i.e., municipalities, regions and private funds. These will be explored in each of the regions and should give good opportunities in most cases. The self-assessment of the investment readiness level should be seen as a reflection of maturity of the business plan.

The overall conclusions are that the budgets developed so far will need more focus on the weak points pinpointed in this report, seeking to reduce costs and/or increase revenues. In general, it is difficult to establish this type of hub in a competitive educational system (very different in each region), but the needs are clear. Overall, it seems like the Irish and Finnish BBECs are most realistic in economic and financial terms, which may be explained by a more national based approach in these centres compared to some other centres. However, all six BBECs have potential for success.

Introduction and background

WP3 provides detailed plans for implementation of the BBEC covering vocational, academic, and life-long learning, in a coordinated and consistent form. The WP addresses the centres' financial and non-financial issues including design of the financing plan, operational and legal requirements and needed resources, to support their flexible, reliable, and sustainable operations. The specific objective of Task 3.3 is to provide an economic analysis of the feasibility of the centres, including a detailed screening of potential funding sources and models.

The objective of this report is to perform a comparative analysis and assessment of six individual budgets and financial plans from each of the six BBECs to evaluate economic and financial sustainability. This is a core goal of the feasibility of the six BBECs and should be seen alongside D 3.2 on the governance structures of the BBECs and D 3.4 on the training activities of the BBECs.

The work has had two parallel subtasks a) on evaluating the realistic budgets and financial plans of the BBECs, led by FBCD and b) an overview of additional funding sources from the BBEC ecosystem as well as an investment readiness self-assessment, led by SIE. In both cases stakeholders were involved through workshops.

This work combines the two aspects and gives key information about the economic sustainability of the six BBECs. However, this is the first step in a longer process for the individual BBECs to be able to present sustainable economic and financially centres.

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Part 1. Realistic budget and financial plans for each of the six BBecs

Methodology

Each budget contains information about investments, capital expenditures (CapEx), operating expenses (OpEx), and revenues. CapEx (Capital Expenditure) refers to the funds invested to acquire, upgrade, or maintain assets like buildings, equipment, or infrastructure. Capital expenditures are typically one-time or long-term investments.

OpEx (Operating Expense) represents the ongoing costs to operate ongoing activities. Operating expenses include items such as employee salaries, rent, utilities, marketing expenses and other costs necessary to keep the centre running. The method used aims to identify similarities, differences, and trends across the budgets, enabling an assessment of their financial performance and viability.

Data for the report is worked out by each BBEC individually as part of task 3.3. The budgets should be made for Years 1, 2 and 3-5, i.e., cover a total of five years, and be organized in a standardized format for consistency. A standardized template in Excel and Word was given at the beginning of the task.

Data from individual budgets were standardized into different accounts in this report to ensure consistency and comparability. The data was categorized in the work of summarizing different aspects of budgets. Data from the different BBECs were put into tables for comparison needs.

To evaluate the six BBECs during their initial five years, the budgets in this report have been consolidated for years 1-5. In cases where a five-year plan was not available, years 2 or 3 are considered representative of the subsequent years.

The results in the coming sections show large differences in the six ways to set up a budget and this has made the comparison a difficult task. However, the main outcome of this should be that we learn from each other's, and this report will inspire for next budget calculations in the six cases.

Results

The specific work on the economic plans reported from each BBE is found in Annex 2 and the corresponding excel sheets are only gives as exemplifying screenshots.

Necessary investments

The necessary investments for most BBECs are included in Capex for year one of the budget. For Eastern Europe BBEC, part of the investments is also in years three and four.

In the following CaPex and Investments are assumed to be included in CaPex and seen for a period of five years.

Capital expenditures (CapEx)

BBEC	Expenses	Comments
Eastern Europe	245.000	Office space, Equipment, Web and materials
Finland	37.000	Concept development and Online Platform (All year 1)
Germany	142.000	Concept development, equipment and travel- 9.000 covered by in-kind (university)
Ireland	15.000	Only website development is calculated as CaPex.
Mediterranean	89.300	Consortium creation and Center establishment, Legal advisory, Travel Costs
Denmark	95.000	Organization, concept development and Website/Platform

In the different geographic regions, there exist various models for establishing the BioBBEC. Most of these models primarily involve investments in concept development, organizational infrastructure, and the creation of a web platform or website.

However, the BBEC in Eastern Europe has devised a plan that goes beyond the standard approach. Their plan entails the modernization of offices (year 3 and 4) and the acquisition of equipment specifically aimed at establishing dedicated workspaces for individuals operating within the centre (year 1).

For Finnish BBEC there will mostly be CapEx costs in year 1, since only website-domain licenses is calculated in.

German centre calculates a Salary of 120.000 the first year for concept development. Hence all costs for the first year are assumed to be CapEx.

In the Irish BBEC only website development is calculated into Capex. It is assumed that 1st year OpEx cost will be used for concept development.

CapEx for Danish BBEC includes help from experts, legal advisers and other external assistance for concept development.

Operational expenses – OPEX

Management

BBEC	Expenses	Comments
Eastern Europe	800.000	
Finland	762.000	Coordinator and Key actors
Germany	569.825	Person 1 and Person 2
Ireland	638.286	
Mediterranean	540.000	Director and Community manager
Denmark	400.000	Coordinator

Across all partners, the management component constitutes the largest portion of operating expenses (OpEx) as it plays a crucial role in overseeing and facilitating activities within the centers. The significant variances in management costs can be attributed to the diverse approaches employed in organizing the work within each partner's centre.

Teachers and other staff

BBEC	Expenses	Comments
Eastern Europe	243.000	External assistance
Finland	0	No teachers paid by BBEC
Germany	455.860	Person 3 and 4
Ireland	54.000	External assistance
Mediterranean	292.600	External assistance, experts etc.
Denmark	0	Courses are held by partners without payment through the BBEC

The teaching aspect in most of the centers is primarily based on activities where Universities and different partners are accomplishing the teaching at courses. Costs in this category are mostly for buying expertise for course development and creating online teaching material.

Buildings

BBEC	Expenses	Comments
Eastern Europe	23.500	Costs for venues
Finland	0	No costs included due to university buildings
Germany	15.000	Offices and its maintenance
Ireland	0	University buildings (costs for venues under other expenses)
Mediterranean	6.000	Renting venues
Denmark	0	Covered by Institutional capacity costs

The centers have not allocated a specific budget for housing offices within their current facilities, as it is anticipated that they will be established within existing environments at universities and clusters. Nevertheless, the Danish and Eastern European centers have included these expenses as part of their overall "Institutional capacity costs."

Administrative costs

BBEC	Expenses	Comments
Eastern Europe	0	Part of management costs
Finland	0	Part of management costs
Germany	25.000	Secretary and supplies
Ireland	0	
Mediterranean	55.000	Secretary and translation
Denmark	0	Part of management and Institutional capacity costs

Admin costs are in four cases encountered within the management budgets or as part of “Institutional capacity costs”, which enables the organizations to use existing resources to handle administrative roles.

Marketing/website

BBEC	Expenses	Comments
Eastern Europe	243.000	
Finland	30.000	
Germany	0	
Ireland	40.000	Website, tools and more (salaries stem from management)
Mediterranean		
Denmark	225.000	Coordinator and website management

Marketing and website are costs for developing running online platforms/web and for various communication materials for each BBEC. The Mediterranean BBEC has budgeted IT experts that might be needed for this task. These costs are summed up in other accounts.

Other expenses

BBEC	Expenses	Comments
Eastern Europe	221.000	IT, Catering and Travel costs
Finland	0	
Germany	36.460	Travel and course expenses
Ireland	25.000	Travel, Catering, Venues
Mediterranean	0	
Denmark	75.000	Travel, Catering, venues

Local /national BBECs will naturally have lower travel costs, whereas Eastern European has the largest costs. The Mediterranean BBEC is planned to be completely virtual, thus no travel costs in the budget.

Institutional capacity costs (Offices, accountancy, it-support etc.)

BBEC	Expenses	Comments
Eastern Europe	321.875	INDIRECT (25% Operational costs)
Finland	0	
Germany	0	
Ireland	0	
Mediterranean	0	
Denmark	175.000	Indirect costs for admin, offices etc.

Institutional capacity costs are costs for getting support from the home organization to fulfil the tasks i.e., cost of offices, accountancy and it-support. Here, four BBECs expect to have the office expenses covered by the hosting institution and have not been included in the budgets.

Origin of revenues (including alternative sources) and cost => Profit/ loss statement

The sources of revenue across the BBECs are diverse and exhibit significant variations. In particular, the Eastern Europe centre relies heavily on funds obtained through various EU projects, whereas other centres have a more evenly distributed revenue profile.

Public funding

BBEC		Comments
Eastern Europe	1.872.919	Fundings from EU projects and national programs
Finland	0	
Germany	711.000	State (133.000 year 1) and University (9.000/year 1,2,3,4,5) projects (533.000 year 2,3,4,5)
Ireland	772.286	Projects and other public funding
Mediterranean	325.000	Various projects
Denmark	396.000	Regional and national funding

For most BBECs a substantial share of funding come from public funding, the percentages are given here:

- Eastern Europe 85%
- Finland 0%
- Germany 83%
- Ireland 100%
- Mediterranean 34%
- Danish 45%

The public funding at the Finish BBEC is budgeted as 0 €, but it is expected that there will be possible public funding for 150. – 300.000 €. The German BBEC expects funding from the University, State and from various projects through the years.

Participants payments

BBEC		Comments
Eastern Europe	255.000	Membership fees and courses (Year 5)
Finland	605.000	Key Actor Participation
Germany	0	
Ireland	0	No participator payments
Mediterranean	250.000	Member fees and participation fees
Denmark	470.000	Partner fees for being part of the centre

The majority of BBECs generate revenue through participant payments, which contribute to their overall revenue stream. This revenue is derived from partners paying a membership fee to access the BBEC online and other services. However, the revenue from selling courses is relatively minimal

since this aspect predominantly occurs at the partner level and is therefore included in their respective revenue.

Other sources of revenues

BBEC		Comments
Eastern Europe	70.000	Access to web and other services (From year 5)
Finland	250.000	Services provided by BBEC
Germany	0	
Ireland	0	
Mediterranean	375.000	In kind contributions from university
Denmark	0	

Discussion and sustainability assessment

This assessment is based on the data from each BBEC presented in the above sections, summarized into a comparable table. The table consists of sums for CapEx, OpEx, Revenues and a balance calculated from these data for each BBEC over a five-year period.

The results in the previous sections show large differences in the six ways to set up a budget and this has made the comparison a difficult task. However, the main outcome of this should be that we learn from each other's, and this report will inspire for next budget calculations in the six cases.

The comparison table will serve as an aid to present the findings, allowing for an easy comparison of the economic indicators across the six BBECs. It gives an overview of their overall financial health and sustainability.

The comparative table highlights significant variations in the operational plans and perceived sustainability of each BBEC over a five-year timeframe, encompassing all costs and revenues.

BBEC	Capex	Opex	Revenue	Balance
Eastern Europe	245.000	1.852.375	2.197.919	100.544
Finland	37.000	792.000	855.000	26.000
Germany	142.000	1.102.145	711.000	-533.145
Ireland	15.000	757.286	797.286	25.000
Mediterranean	89.300	893.600	950.000	-32.900
Denmark	95.000	875.000	866.000	-104.000

Certain BBECs exhibit negative balances over the full period of five years, due to insufficient revenues in relation to projected costs. This situation can be attributed, in part, to certain centres' expectations that partners (such as universities) would contribute through non-monetary means, which were not factored into the economic model. Conversely, other centres have incorporated these contributions within their economic model.

In essence, the continued existence of the centres relies on their capacity to generate income. For certain centres, a notable portion of their funding hinges on project applications, which lack a guarantee of success. Consequently, it is imperative to strive towards establishing dependable and sustainable revenue streams, to secure the centres' long-term viability.

In most BBEC models, university activities are based on the actual cost at the university, including overhead and other costs besides direct activity-based costs, there is a specific consideration for teaching salaries. These salaries are typically not included in the BBEC (Bio Based Educational Center) budgets since they are covered by the educational institutions themselves. As a result, a separate model needs to be developed to account for the payment of teaching salaries from the course or activity fees in each case. However, the salaries of the teaching staff involved in delivering the course or activity are not part of the direct activity-based costs. Instead, the educational institution

as a whole covers these salaries. This could be done through its general budget, separate funding for teaching staff, or other mechanisms.

In addition to teaching salaries, there are often other "in-kind" contributions some BBECs that need to be specified when developing the full budget model. These in-kind contributions refer to non-monetary resources or services that are provided to support the development of new activities, courses, or educational initiatives within some BBECs.

When creating new activities or courses, BBECs may receive support from external organizations, industry partners, or government agencies. These contributions can include access to specialized equipment or facilities, provision of materials or supplies, assistance from subject matter experts, or even grants and funding for specific projects.

While these in-kind contributions do not involve direct financial transactions, they represent valuable resources that contribute to the overall functioning and success of the BBEC. Therefore, it is important to identify and specify these contributions when developing the full budget model. By incorporating in-kind contributions into the budget model, BBECs can accurately account for the resources and support they receive from external sources. This allows for a more comprehensive understanding of the total costs and benefits associated with developing new activities, courses, or educational programs.

Furthermore, specifying these in-kind contributions helps to demonstrate the collaborative nature of the BBEC and its connections to external stakeholders. It also enables the educational institution to showcase the value of partnerships and their impact on enhancing the learning experience for students.

When developing the full budget model, it is essential to document and quantify these in-kind contributions. This involves assigning a value or cost estimate to the resources or services received. This estimation process may involve consulting with the contributing organizations or conducting market research to determine the fair value of the provided resources.

The financial calculations for the BBECs are expected to be complete, but since none of the centres have been established and there are no plans to establish them in the next six months, efforts should be focused on achieving a balance between costs and revenues.

Three of the BBECs currently have a negative balance. This suggests that the projected expenses for these centres exceed their anticipated income. This situation indicates that further work needs to be done to address this imbalance. To rectify the negative balance, the BBECs must explore strategies to either increase revenues, reduce costs, or implement a combination of both. Increasing revenues can be achieved through various means such as attracting more participants, offering additional courses or programs, exploring partnerships with industry or government entities, or seeking alternative funding sources.

On the other hand, some other BBECs may have been overly optimistic in terms of securing external public funding. Particularly, it highlights the Eastern Europe BBEC as being different in this regard. This implies that these centres may have relied heavily on public funding sources to cover their costs, but the expected funding may not materialize as planned.

In this case, it becomes crucial for these BBECs to reassess their financial projections and explore alternative funding options or adjust their budgetary expectations. Overall, it must be the importance of achieving a balance must be emphasized. It indicates that further work needs to be done to address negative balances by either increasing revenues, reducing costs, or re-examining funding expectations. By carefully assessing and adjusting their financial strategies, the BBECs can enhance their financial sustainability and ensure their long-term success.

The above highlights that the six biobased educational BBECs operate based on different operational models and financial approaches, making direct comparisons between them challenging. However, based on the budgets presented over a five-year period, the Finnish and Irish BBECs appear to have better financial balance, while the Danish and German centres need to work on developing more sustainable models.

The Finnish and Irish BBECs are in better balance due to their operational models, which rely on regional or national activities. This simplifies their budgets as they involve only one organization directly responsible for running the BBEC. These centres seem to have achieved a more favourable financial situation.

Conversely, the German and Danish BBECs have high negative balances, indicating a need for adjustments to ensure long-term sustainability. The German BBEC is advised to examine the financial aspects of using an in-kind model. This includes ensuring that costs and revenues based on in-kind contributions are in balance, addressing any discrepancies.

The Danish BBEC, on the other hand, needs to find ways to generate higher revenues to align with the costs of running the centre. Exploring alternative financing models, such as offering additional services for partners, could be considered to cover operational costs more effectively.

The Mediterranean BBEC has a minor negative balance and appears to have a sustainable model for the first five years. However, the reliance on in-kind contributions from partner universities may not be a sustainable source in the long run. This suggests the need to diversify funding sources or explore additional revenue streams to ensure the centre's long-term financial stability.

Part 2. Public and private funding additional opportunities

BBECs might need additional funds to carry out the needed projects and activities to ensure lifelong performance after the projects' afterlife. A screening of European public and private opportunities has been carried out and the result of this is presented in Annex 3.

External financing sources do not include an analysis of bank financing as this is linked to the regional context and needs to be analysed on a case-by-case basis.

During the identification phase of funding and financing sources, two main pathways have been explored to ease the classification of the sourced and collected information, public and private financing sources:

- **Private financing sources** underline entities and organizations that support business potential through an equity-based model. Following this model, the investees (in this case the different BBECs) receive financing in exchange for a proportional ownership stake in the business activity. Private institutions engage in this model due to the anticipated positive returns within a specified period.
- **Public funding sources**, on the other hand, contribute to the development and growth through loan-based models, where investees are supposed to get a lump sum funding amount to finance their business activities that the funding sources are aiming to fund. Both private and financing sources are outstanding enablers for the successful scaling up of products or services during the market and commercialization roadmap.

Both schemes are worth considering as a meaningful nature of "funds" without high economic return, such as grants in public entities or donations in private institutions.

The diagram in Figure 1 illustrates the two types of schemes (public/private) defined within groups based on their investment focus. The schemes are also classified according to the type of return they provide in the context of the BIOBEC project: social return, traditional/economic return, and impact return. Impact return, also known as the "double return" approach, refers to investments that expect high economic returns along with environmental and social benefits. In such cases, economic returns may be lower compared to investments solely driven by financial profitability. Investments focused solely on social benefits are considered as seeking social returns.

By considering these different funding sources and their distinct characteristics, it becomes possible to explore various opportunities and identify the most suitable funding options for bioeconomy education centres and their lifelong performance beyond project lifecycles.

Figure 1 Funding opportunities (Public & Private)

The different sources presented in Annex 3 have been identified as potential funding opportunities for the different BBECs.

Recommended funds for each region

Among all the different opportunities envisaged in the Annex 3, the following ones are selected to deep dive into their requirements, as they deliver a balanced approach between the requirements to be spotted by the BBECs and enough funding resources to perform as a valuable revenue source in the short-term.

BBEC	Funding Programme	Type of Finance	Topic	Description	Link
German	Spitze auf den Land! Technologieführer (ELR)	Grant	Technological leadership and rural development	<i>"Excellence in the Countryside"</i> , supports technological leaders in rural areas. It provides financial assistance to businesses and organizations in rural regions to develop and implement innovative projects. The program aims to strengthen the economic potential of rural areas, including the bioeconomy sector.	Link
Danish	Central Denmark Region	Courses	Developing new courses, not formal education	The focus is to train the teacher. You must be an educational inst.	Link
Finnish	Regional Council of North Karelia	Structural funding, JTF	Internationalization, investment, growing and scale-up services	Regional development. It is responsible for regional planning and general coordination of regional development programs related to national and EU structural funds.	Link
Eastern-Central	FENG.02.17 Development of the cluster offer for companies	European	European Funds for Modern Economy	The action is aimed at: strengthening the professionalization of the activities of coordinators of supra-regional growth clusters, aspiring to obtain the status of National Key Clusters, to develop an innovative service offer for companies in the field of R&D&I.	Link
Mediterranean (ES)	Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica y el Reto Demográfico (MITECO)	National Grant	Bioeconomy promotion	The purpose of the call is to regulate the granting of grants for the financing of transformative projects that contribute to the promotion of the bioeconomy, ecological transition, demographic challenge, and the strengthening of capacities and creation of opportunities in rural areas.	Link
Mediterranean (IT)	Regional funds for Education and Training	National Grant	Adult education and training funding	Courses are financed through other funds and contributions from the Regions and local authorities.	Link

Irish	Enterprise Ireland	Grant	Green Transition Fund & Digital Transition Fund	<p>Enterprise Ireland is the state agency responsible for supporting the development of manufacturing and internationally traded services companies. We provide funding and supports for companies - from entrepreneurs with business propositions for a high potential start-up through to large companies expanding their activities, improving efficiency and growing international sales. GREEN TRANSITION FUND and the DIGITAL TRANSITION FUND</p>	Link
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Part 3 Investment Readiness Level

Introduction

The investment process when facing potential funders and partnership usually embraces potential risks and sustainability challenges that are likely to influence the final outcomes of these agreements. The Investment Readiness Level (IRL) is a business concept to assess how prepared and attractive a project or an organization is to a potential investor. It provides an accurate framework for evaluating the readiness an entity is to secure private funding and engage investment activities. By performing IRL, the different BBECs will set the level of development, feasibility and potential return on investment of their project.

The IRL assessment underlines various aspects of a project, such as the market potential, business model, team expertise, financial projects or scalability ratio. The assessment enables the identification of strengths, weaknesses and areas that needs to be improved to increase IRL scoring.

Methodology

The Investment Readiness Level is a tool that is aiming to identify strengths and weaknesses using a multidimensional approach and develop a tailor-made action plan to address the needs and challenges. Based on the scores obtained from the IRL assessment, each BBEC will be driven towards tailored strategy to improve the specific aspects where improvement is needed as well as encourage to follow a specific funding strategy to fit within its requirements.

The IRL is the gateway to ensure a financial sustainable implementation of the BBECs and therefore secure its investment process when facing potential funders opportunities of partnership.

The IRL is addressed to be conducted in an iterative way:

- **Step 1:** Self-Assessment
- **Step 2:** Workshop conducted by SIE where the results will be analysed and discussed.
- **Step 3:** After self-assessment is performed and workshop is conducted, SIE will produce a brief IRL assessment document with both evaluations, giving a last overall validation and presenting the level of investment and which are the most accurate funding sources to apply for, in accordance with both the evaluations and the provided feedback.
- **Step 4:** Follow-up activities will be also addressed.

Self-Assessment

The self-assessment is a tool that is designed to evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of innovative education centres that focus on enhancing the bio-based economy. The assessment is divided into six dimensions: competence and structure of the education centre, markets, talent, technology landscape, financials, and economic projections.

Each of the six dimensions is further broken down into three questions, which are designed to help evaluate the specific case of the innovative education centre being assessed. The questions are rated on a scale from 0 to 9, with 0 indicating that nothing has been developed in that area and 9 indicating that the area is fully developed and optimized.

The purpose of the self-assessment is to provide a comprehensive evaluation of each innovative education centre, with the goal of identifying strengths and weaknesses in each of the six dimensions. The assessment can be used by individuals or organizations that are looking to develop or invest in innovative education centres in the bio-based economy sector.

By using the self-assessment, individuals and organizations can gain a better understanding of the current state of innovative education centres, as well as identify areas for improvement or potential opportunities for growth. This can help individuals and organizations make more informed decisions about which innovative education centres to invest in, or how to improve existing education centres in order to maximize their impact on the bio-based economy.

- **A) Competence and structure of the BBEC:** This dimension assesses the competency and structure of the leadership team and staff of the innovative education centre. The questions in this dimension are designed to evaluate the level of expertise and experience of the CEO, board members, and employees, as well as the overall structure and organization of the education centre.
- **B) Markets:** This dimension evaluates the market potential of the innovative education centre. The questions in this dimension are designed to assess the size and growth potential of the target market, as well as the unique value proposition that the education centre offers to its target market.
- **C) Talent:** This dimension assesses the quality and availability of talent within the innovative education centre. The questions in this dimension are designed to evaluate the education centre's strategy for attracting and retaining top talent, as well as its culture of learning and professional development.
- **D) Technology landscape:** This dimension evaluates the education centre's use of technology in its teaching practices and curriculum. The questions in this dimension are designed to assess the education centre's access to technology tools and hardware, as well as its plan for integrating technology into its teaching practices.
- **E) Financials:** This dimension assesses the financial sustainability of the innovative education centre. The questions in this dimension are designed to evaluate the education centre's business model, as well as its projected revenue, expenses, and profits.
- **F) Economic:** This dimension evaluates the potential economic impact of the innovative education centre on the local community. The questions in this dimension are designed to assess the education centre's ability to create jobs and increase productivity, as well as its potential risks or challenges.

It is expected to discuss and reach agreement on which are the most accurate questions / statements that each BBEC will assess for each dimension. A first rough draft has been shared as per following table:

Section	Question	Answer Type
Competence and structure of the BBEC	The CEO/ chairperson/ board member has competencies relevant for the company and leadership	1-10 score
	The company is well structured and divided into clearly focused departments (communications/marketing, sales, business, finance and accounting, HR, production, product development, project management).	1-10 score
	The employees/ teams cover all relevant competencies (Communication/ Marketing, Sales, Business, Finance, HR Management, IT) needed.	1-10 score
Markets	The target market for the education center is clearly defined and understood.	1-10 score
	The target market is growing and offers significant potential for the education center.	1-10 score
	The education center has a unique value proposition that addresses the specific needs and preferences of the target market.	1-10 score
Talent	The education center has a clear and well-defined strategy for attracting and retaining top talent.	1-10 score
	The education center has a strong culture of learning and professional development.	1-10 score
	The education center has a diverse and inclusive workforce that reflects the community it serves.	1-10 score
Technology landscape	The education center is up-to-date with the latest technological developments in the field of education.	1-10 score
	The education center has access to the necessary hardware, software, and other tools needed to deliver high-quality education.	1-10 score
	The education center has a clear plan for integrating technology into its teaching practices and curriculum.	1-10 score
Financials	The education center has a clear and sustainable business model.	1-10 score
	The education center has identified potential sources of funding, such as grants, loans, or investors.	1-10 score
	The education center has a detailed financial plan that includes projected revenue, expenses, and profits.	1-10 score
Economic projections	The education center has identified potential economic benefits, such as job creation or increased productivity, for the local community.	1-10 score
	The education center has a clear plan for measuring and tracking its economic impact.	1-10 score
	The education center has identified potential risks or challenges that could impact its economic projections, such as changes in the market or regulatory environment.	1-10 score

MEDITERRANEAN BBEC

Table 1 Mediterranean BBEC IRL assessment

Section	Question	Score	Reason
Competence and structure of the BBEC	The CEO/ chairperson/ board member has competencies relevant for the company and leadership	7	Company website, LinkedIn profiles of the leadership team, and any available media coverage or press releases mentioning their professional background.
	The company is well structured and divided into clearly focused departments (communications/marketing, sales, business, finance and accounting, HR, production, product development, project management).	6	Company website, information from employees or former employees, and any available media coverage or press releases mentioning the company's organizational structure.
	The employees/ teams cover all relevant competencies (Communication/ Marketing, Sales, Business, Finance, HR Management, IT) needed.	5	Job postings or descriptions, information from employees or former employees, and any available media coverage or press releases mentioning the company's workforce or staffing strategy.
Markets	The target market for the education centre is clearly defined and understood.	8	Market analysis report conducted by BBEC. The targeted market for the MED BBEC is wide range of curricula in sectors related to the Bioeconomy (agriculture, biology, engineering). Main value chain is defined (food and food waste)
	The target market is growing and offers significant potential for the education centre.	7	Market analysis report conducted in D1.1 "Report on European and regional analysis of the needs, opportunities, and expectations to bio-based education/training models"
	The education centre has a unique value proposition that addresses the specific needs and preferences of the target market.	4	It can be said that MED BBEC is still not ready to fulfil all the potentially requested courses to deliver its promised value proposition.
Talent	The education centre has a clear and well-defined strategy for attracting and retaining top talent.	3	It might have been previously addressed, but still not in place
	The education centre has a strong culture of learning and professional development.	3	Same as above
	The education centre has a diverse and inclusive workforce that reflects the community it serves.	3	Same as above
Technology landscape	The education centre is up-to-date with the latest technological developments in the field of education.	5	New education tools (e.g. online courses and digital solutions in general, but also learning paths connecting education and knowledge/innovation) and approaches to education (e.g. action learning, Mobilisation and Mutual learning) need to be taken into account in order to match the current and future needs.

	The education centre has access to the necessary hardware, software, and other tools needed to deliver high-quality education.	3	Additional investment will be required to purchase hardware and software tools to deliver promised high-quality education. In the beginning, leveraging the technological structure of some partners will assist to kickstart the programmes, but still a lower score in this level.
	The education centre has a clear plan for integrating technology into its teaching practices and curriculum.	8	There is a clear plan for integrating technology into their teaching practices and curriculums. Based on information provided by the BBEC regarding their plans for integrating technology into their teaching practices and curriculum, as well as their investment in instructor training programs.
Financials	The education centre has a clear and sustainable business model.	4	The "Overall exploitation and sustainability plan" will be the milestone to confirm that this question can be qualified higher. So far, the business model is in a early-starting point.
	The education centre has identified potential sources of funding, such as grants, loans, or investors.	6	It is planned to be developed (financial plan with projected revenue, expenses and profits) alongside WP3, therefore when WP3 is ended, it is supposed to be addressed in a starting way; but will be need to be fine-tune to qualify higher
	The education centre has a detailed financial plan that includes projected revenue, expenses, and profits.	6	It is planned to be developed (financial plan with projected revenue, expenses and profits) alongside WP3, therefore when WP3 is ended, it is supposed to be addressed in a starting way; but will be need to be fine-tune to qualify higher
Economic projections	The education centre has identified potential economic benefits, such as job creation or increased productivity, for the local community.	9	Based on the information gathered in the co-creation workshop, there is a "Strong needs of professionals with skills in bio-based pilot plants and biomasses managements. Currently, there is no connection with bio-economy in conventional technical courses. Mandatory to train professional figures such as technicians in a double key: 1) training/support to the company 2) case study of how to implement a training course in bio-economy".
	The education centre has a clear plan for measuring and tracking its economic impact.	3	The BBEC has drafted some plans for measuring and tracking its economic impact, but they are not well-defined or detailed.
	The education centre has identified potential risks or challenges that could impact its economic projections, such as changes in the market or regulatory environment.	7	Based on the information provided in D1.1 Report on European and regional analysis of the needs, opportunities and expectations to bio-based education training models

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CENTRAL-EAST BBEC

Table 2 Central-East BBEC IRL assessment

Section	Question	Score	Reason
Competence and structure of the BBEC	The CEO/ chairperson/ board member has competencies relevant for the company and leadership	9	The chairperson and board will be selected from people with appropriate qualifications in managing various types of organizations, including hubs.
	The company is well structured and divided into clearly focused departments (communications/marketing, sales, business, finance and accounting, HR, production, product development, project management).	9	The structure defined in the Governance Plan is adequate to the planned activities and capabilities of the organization. It is flexible, but at the same time clearly indicates individual tasks. The structure is inclusive, enabling the inclusion of new working groups composed of relevant actors.
	The employees/ teams cover all relevant competencies (Communication/ Marketing, Sales, Business, Finance, HR Management, IT) needed.	8	The current team covers all the key aspects indicated. The only gap is in sales and marketing.
Markets	The target market for the education centre is clearly defined and understood.	5	The education centre market is as precisely defined as possible at the moment. Bioeconomy in Eastern Europe is still a developing field. The level of understanding in society and industry is low. In addition, there are no adopted national strategies for bioeconomy in the region (currently only Latvia), which additionally makes it difficult to identify the target market.
	The target market is growing and offers significant potential for the education centre.	8	The lack of awareness is not the same as the huge potential (e.g. biomass, scientific achievements) that is in the region. The market is growing significantly, and this is a trend that will continue for years to come.
	The education centre has a unique value proposition that addresses the specific needs and preferences of the target market.	8	Within the project, the needs and expectations of relevant stakeholders were examined in order to select the appropriate value proposition. However, the market is still evolving and therefore further research and update of the value proposition is necessary.
Talent	The education centre has a clear and well-defined strategy for attracting and retaining top talent.	6	With the development of awareness of the bioeconomy in the region and setting directions for development at the government level, it will be possible to upgrade the Centre's offer so that it engages top talents.
	The education centre has a strong culture of learning and professional development.	9	The centre will be focused on continuous learning, tracking the changing environment and trends. The centre must be flexible to follow the developing bioeconomy of the region.
	The education centre has a diverse and inclusive workforce that reflects the community it serves.	7	Currently, people with very diverse backgrounds are connected to the centre. The Centre integrates entities from very different fields of bioeconomy and gives the opportunity to other entities to join the work.

Technology landscape	The education centre is up-to-date with the latest technological developments in the field of education.	8	The Centre plans extensive cooperation with research units and universities that have the appropriate scientific base and training staff to respond to the needs of the industry.
	The education centre has access to the necessary hardware, software, and other tools needed to deliver high-quality education.	5	The Centre plans extensive cooperation with research units and universities that have the appropriate scientific base and training staff to respond to the needs of the industry. However, it will be necessary to purchase hardware and software for hybrid events, which will be related to the activities undertaken in the field of education or remote networking.
	The education centre has a clear plan for integrating technology into its teaching practices and curriculum.	8	The Centre plans extensive cooperation with research units and universities that have the appropriate scientific base and training staff to respond to the needs of the industry. It is plan to implement technology in the practice of the Centre.
Financials	The education centre has a clear and sustainable business model.	8	The centre has a clear and viable business model. It is developed for the moment, considering the current market conditions, the political situation and the possibilities of partners. Due to the necessary development of the bioeconomy ecosystem, it is necessary to use available external funds. However, they will allow to create capacity, expand the base of partners, build market value that will contribute to maintaining revenue streams.
	The education centre has identified potential sources of funding, such as grants, loans, or investors.	10	Potential sources of external financing were thoroughly analysed. Both at the level of the EU, international programs and national funds, it was possible to identify many opportunities for the development of the Centre. This shows that his idea is in line with the plans of financing institutions and countries in Eastern Europe.
	The education centre has a detailed financial plan that includes projected revenue, expenses, and profits.	8	Centre has developed a detailed financial plan. It contains a detailed list of investment and operating costs in the perspective of 5 years. In addition, the currently revenue streams have been indicated. However, they will be updated as a result of the development of regional policies in the countries of the region and adapted to the directions of the bioeconomy strategy. The centre will continuously develop its offer and value proposition in order to flexibly adapt to the market.
Economic projections	The education centre has identified potential economic benefits, such as job creation or increased productivity, for the local community.	6	When developing the action plan for the next 5 years, the need to increase the number of employees was identified to cope with the development of the centre's activities.
	The education centre has a clear plan for measuring and tracking its economic impact.	7	The partners who are to create the Centre have staff with expert analytical knowledge in the field of finance. Economic impact will be continuously monitored and action plans for funding will be periodically updated.

	<p>The education centre has identified potential risks or challenges that could impact its economic projections, such as changes in the market or regulatory environment.</p>	<p>8</p>	<p>When working on the financial model, the high uncertainty of the directions of bioeconomy development in the region was considered. Most of the countries in the region do not have an approved vision of development, therefore it will be necessary to follow this process and actively respond to the actions of decision-makers.</p>
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German BBEC

Table 3 German BBEC IRL assessment

Section	Question	Score	Reason
Competence and structure of the BBEC	The CEO/ chairperson/ board member has competencies relevant for the company and leadership	3	The CEO/ chairperson is not yet being selected but with the activities that are being carried out today, the leader would be the current leader of the Bioeconomy Office with the support of the Chief Bioeconomy Officer. They have the relevant competence for leading the BBEC, however the current resources (time availability) are not enough and would not allow to carry out all the necessary work needed for the BBEC operation. After a selection process, we believe this role can be taken by a proficient employee capable of leading the BBEC.
	The company is well structured and divided into clearly focused departments (communications/marketing, sales, business, finance and accounting, HR, production, product development, project management).	4	As the German BBEC will be part of the university, there is already a well-organized structure that serves as basis for the creation, refinement and alignment of the new proposed governance structure of the BBEC. But as it is not yet implemented, the score is quite low.
	The employees/ teams cover all relevant competencies (Communication/ Marketing, Sales, Business, Finance, HR Management, IT) needed.	3	The team has not yet been selected but the current labour force covers most of the relevant competences needed for the operation of the BBEC. As with the CEO, the current resources are not enough for the vision of the BBEC and that is why the score is low. Besides, some gaps still need to be addressed, for example in terms of project skills, finance and marketing.
Markets	The target market for the education centre is clearly defined and understood.	5	The target market is clearly defined, but implementation and more research may be needed to fully understand it and reach it
	The target market is growing and offers significant potential for the education centre.	7	The increasing number of persons involved in bioeconomy in the region and the discussion with relevant stakeholders demonstrates the need and potential of the BBEC and its value proposition
	The education centre has a unique value proposition that addresses the specific needs and preferences of the target market.	5	The BBEC has a unique value proposition, but some needs and preferences of the target market are still not covered completely with the current activities.
Talent	The education centre has a clear and well-defined strategy for attracting and retaining top talent.	4	The current structure, in which the BBEC will potentially be built upon, has limited strategies to attract and retain top talent. The salaries cannot compete with the competence in the industry sector. However, there are multiple benefits such as networking opportunities, independency in work, on-the-job training options, access to different disciplinary expertise, among others. Therefore, a better strategy must be developed.
	The education centre has a strong culture of learning and professional development.	7	The current structure and future education centre environment have a culture that values learning and encourages professional development opportunities for employees as it is involved in the University environment

	The education centre has a diverse and inclusive workforce that reflects the community it serves.	6	The current structure and future education centre environment is diverse in nature in terms of cultures and disciplines. This diversity may need to be further developed when the BBEC is implemented.
Technology landscape	The education centre is up-to-date with the latest technological developments in the field of education.	7	The University and therefore the BBEC have access to different technological developments in the educational field. However, the BBEC would potentially need access to new technologies.
	The education centre has access to the necessary hardware, software, and other tools needed to deliver high-quality education.	8	The BBEC have access to hardware, software and tools needed to deliver high quality education as it is part of the university.
	The education centre has a clear plan for integrating technology into its teaching practices and curriculum.	5	The BBEC does not have yet a clear plan for integrating technology into their teaching practices and curriculum because it depends on the demand of the courses. Investments, research, cooperation and implementation may be further needed.
Financials	The education centre has a clear and sustainable business model.	6	The BBEC has a clear business model. However as the income streams come specifically from projects, the risk is higher than for other business models. However, the network, the infrastructure and governance structure are well-defined. This could increase the possibilities for obtaining funding from projects. More co-funding options need to be developed and implemented to strengthen the business model and its financial elements.
	The education centre has identified potential sources of funding, such as grants, loans, or investors.	6	The education centre has a detailed financial plan that includes projected revenue, expenses, and profits.
	The education centre has a detailed financial plan that includes projected revenue, expenses, and profits.	6	Lacks detailed financial projections
Economic projections	The education centre has identified potential economic benefits, such as job creation or increased productivity, for the local community.	5	Based on the information provided about the BBEC's plans and goals for community engagement and partnerships.
	The education centre has a clear plan for measuring and tracking its economic impact.	1	Based on the information provided about the BBEC's current plans and capabilities for measuring and reporting on economic impact.
	The education centre has identified potential risks or challenges that could impact its economic projections, such as changes in the market or regulatory environment.	1	Based on the information provided about the BBEC's risk assessment and management practices, as well as industry and regulatory trends.

Danish BBEC

Table 4 Danish BBEC IRL assessment

Section	Question	Answer Type	Reason
Competence and structure of the BBEC	The CEO/ chairperson/ board member has competencies relevant for the company and leadership	7	The coordinator of the BIObec will be hired with the right competencies
	The company is well structured and divided into clearly focused departments (communications/marketing, sales, business, finance and accounting, HR, production, product development, project management).	8	The BIObec will be formed by a small organization having one or two employees. Operations (courses etc) will happen by partners
	The employees/ teams cover all relevant competencies (Communication/ Marketing, Sales, Business, Finance, HR Management, IT) needed.	7	
Markets	The target market for the education centre is clearly defined and understood.	6	The target market is broadly defined, but a difficult market to compete in. The BIObec is open to fulfil also new needs of competencies
	The target market is growing and offers significant potential for the education centre.	8	There is a growing interest and need for knowledge in the field of Bioeconomic and the number of courses in these specific fields are few for now. Potentially a growing market
	The education centre has a unique value proposition that addresses the specific needs and preferences of the target market.	8	The value proposition is unique since the BIObec will be a hub for offering existing an all new courses
Talent	The education centre has a clear and well-defined strategy for attracting and retaining top talent.	8	The BIObec is collaborating closely with existing educational institutions, thus using competencies from the partners
	The education centre has a strong culture of learning and professional development.	9	We have a broad variety of partners, each with their culture of learning
	The education centre has a diverse and inclusive workforce that reflects the community it serves.	9	We use mostly workforce from our partners
Technology landscape	The education centre is up-to-date with the latest technological developments in the field of education.	8	Due to partners as they already have most educations, We 'only' miss the cross-over themes
	The education centre has access to the necessary hardware, software, and other tools needed to deliver high-quality education.	8	Due to partners
	The education centre has a clear plan for integrating technology into its teaching practices and curriculum.	8	Due to partners technology and involvement
Financials	The education centre has a clear and sustainable business model.	7	Business model is anchored in existing educational institutions and the BIObec business model is a small 'cooperative' coordinating the relevant activities

	The education centre has identified potential sources of funding, such as grants, loans, or investors.	7	Partly, but not applied yet
	The education centre has a detailed financial plan that includes projected revenue, expenses, and profits.	8	partly, but only for the coordinating hub - the existing educational institutions (VOC and Universities) have their own business models
Economic projections	The education centre has identified potential economic benefits, such as job creation or increased productivity, for the local community.	2	This can only be determined after 1-2 years of existence
	The education centre has a clear plan for measuring and tracking its economic impact.	2	Not yet
	The education centre has identified potential risks or challenges that could impact its economic projections, such as changes in the market or regulatory environment.	6	To a certain extent

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Finnish BBEC

Table 5 Finnish BBEC IRL self-assessment

Section	Question	Answer Type	Reason
Competence and structure of the BBEC	The CEO/ chairperson/ board member has competencies relevant for the company and leadership	10	Relevant members have been contacted during the project from key actor organisations
	The company is well structured and divided into clearly focused departments (communications/marketing, sales, business, finance and accounting, HR, production, product development, project management).	8	The basic structure has been defined, and will not require further departments since it functions as an online platform, some details regarding key actor organisations will be defined still
	The employees/ teams cover all relevant competencies (Communication/ Marketing, Sales, Business, Finance, HR Management, IT) needed.	9	The coordinator of the platform will have strong background in both research and industry, and ecosystem development
Markets	The target market for the education centre is clearly defined and understood.	8	Basic idea is structured but it could be detailed in the future, which companies are being involved, global actors etc.
	The target market is growing and offers significant potential for the education centre.	9	Forest-based bioeconomy offers great potential for research, business and education. North Karelia will put great effort for developing it as well as attracting international talent to the area.
	The education centre has a unique value proposition that addresses the specific needs and preferences of the target market.	9	Value proposition has been defined in meetings with the key actors.
Talent	The education centre has a clear and well-defined strategy for attracting and retaining top talent.	8	This has been discussed in several meetings but could be still clarified with all actors.
	The education centre has a strong culture of learning and professional development.	10	All educational levels are represented in the centre.
	The education centre has a diverse and inclusive workforce that reflects the community it serves.	9	All relevant actors regarding forest-based bioeconomy are involved, however more industry representatives could be involved in the future
Technology landscape	The education centre is up-to-date with the latest technological developments in the field of education.	10	UEF, Karelia and Riveria represent latest technology in FBS education.
	The education centre has access to the necessary hardware, software, and other tools needed to deliver high-quality education.	10	UEF, Karelia and Riveria will provide these
	The education centre has a clear plan for integrating technology into its teaching practices and curriculum.	10	UEF, Karelia and Riveria are responsible for these
Financials	The education centre has a clear and sustainable business model.	9	The sustainable business model has been defined; however the realisation depends on the coordinator organisation

	The education centre has identified potential sources of funding, such as grants, loans, or investors.	8	Potential funding sources have been discussed but the key actor organisation will take the lead in applying such
	The education centre has a detailed financial plan that includes projected revenue, expenses, and profits.	8	A plan has been defined; however this could be further detailed once the governance is decided
Economic projections	The education centre has identified potential economic benefits, such as job creation or increased productivity, for the local community.	10	These have been defined in a earlier project BIOSCOPE
	The education centre has a clear plan for measuring and tracking its economic impact.	8	Some KPIs have been identified and they should be detailed further
	The education centre has identified potential risks or challenges that could impact its economic projections, such as changes in the market or regulatory environment.	6	Some risks and challenges identified in meetings with key actors, but a profound analysis should be executed

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Irish BBEC

Section	Question	Answer Type	Reason
Competence and structure of the BBEC	The CEO/ chairperson/ board member has competencies relevant for the company and leadership	9	Previous experience with similar projects including bioeconomy and education
	The company is well structured and divided into clearly focused departments (communications/marketing, sales, business, finance and accounting, HR, production, product development, project management).	8	The Irish BBEC will be run by separate organisations such as MTU, BiOrbic and other bioeconomy stakeholders that often collaborate.
	The employees/ teams cover all relevant competencies (Communication/ Marketing, Sales, Business, Finance, HR Management, IT) needed.	7	Two employees suggested, but will have access to MTU and IBF resources.
Markets	The target market for the education centre is clearly defined and understood.	8	MTU/ IBF have been working with bioeconomy stakeholders for years including stakeholder engagement within BIOBEC project.
	The target market is growing and offers significant potential for the education centre.	9	There is a clear growth of bioeconomy sector in Ireland with increase in amount of Government funding.
	The education centre has a unique value proposition that addresses the specific needs and preferences of the target market.	8	
Talent	The education centre has a clear and well-defined strategy for attracting and retaining top talent.	8	
	The education centre has a strong culture of learning and professional development.	9	Due to positioning in a University campus
	The education centre has a diverse and inclusive workforce that reflects the community it serves.	10	in line with MTU policy
Technology landscape	The education centre is up-to-date with the latest technological developments in the field of education.	9	Due to positioning in a University campus
	The education centre has access to the necessary hardware, software, and other tools needed to deliver high-quality education.	8	Due to positioning in a University campus
	The education centre has a clear plan for integrating technology into its teaching practices and curriculum.	9	Technology licences have been accounted for
Financials	The education centre has a clear and sustainable business model.	7	reliant on Government funding
	The education centre has identified potential sources of funding, such as grants, loans, or investors.	7	reliant on Government funding
	The education centre has a detailed financial plan that includes projected revenue, expenses, and profits.	9	reliant on Government funding
Economic projections	The education centre has identified potential economic benefits, such as job creation or increased productivity, for the local community.	8	The education centre will provide information on job opportunities and internships available in bioeconomy area.
	The education centre has a clear plan for measuring and tracking its economic impact.	8	
	The education centre has identified potential risks or challenges that could impact its economic projections, such as changes in the market or regulatory environment.	8	change to Government funding mechanisms

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Discussions on the IRL

Based on the self-assessment of the Investment Readiness Levels (IRLs) for the 6 Bio-Based Education Centres (BBECs), we can draw several conclusions and provide valuable insights for each centre. First a single analysis will be carried out and eventually final conclusions will be raised to leverage the potential of each BBECs to be invested with the most suitable funding or financing sources.

- **Mediterranean BBEC**: The center demonstrates a strong competence and structure within the organization, with competent leadership roles and well-defined departments. There is also a good understanding of its target market and how the BBEC will potentially cater to a unique value proposition to the users. However, there is room for improvement in talent attraction and how the technology will be embedded in the teaching practices. Financial planning also demands further attention.
- **Central-East BBEC**: It showcases excellent competence and structure, held by competent leadership and well-defined departments. The strategy for talent attraction and retention, the strong culture of learning and the diverse workforce that will integrate the BBEC are outstanding features, as well as the identified potential funding sources and economic benefits projections. Further focus should be addressed to improve the target market understanding of the specific market needs.
- **German BBEC**: It demonstrates room for improvement in competence and structure section, as well as talent strategies, therefore the center should focus on enhancing and promoting leadership competences and set a cleared department division. Nevertheless, it is stepping onwards in identifying its target market and has already defined a clear and unique value proposition. Efforts on financial planning and economic projects are suggested to further development of the BBEC.
- **Danish BBEC**: It entitles a strong competence and structure; as well as a clear understanding of its target market. The BBEC also has succeeded in defining a unique value proposition. Talent strategies, technology integration and economic projections also show an excellent score, with high outcomes in each of these sections. The focus should be placed on improving how to address potential risks and challenges.

- **Finnish BBEC**: The self-assessment exhibits similar results to the previous BBEC, excelling in competence and structure, highlighting its strong leadership management, and demonstrating a well-defined department layout. Target market and unique proposition, as well as clear understanding of the target market also hit an outstanding score; and it shows good progress in talent strategies, technology integration and financial planning. On the other hand, it must focus its effort in enhancing social return on investment and address potential risks and challenges.
- **Irish BBEC**: It showcases a good level of competence and structure, and a clear understanding of target market to be addressed and how the value proposition will enhance the adoption of its service. It demonstrates also acceptable values in talent strategies, technology integration and financial issues. The centre should be focused again in addressing potential risks and challenges.

All BBECs are highly encouraged to continuously monitor and evaluate their investment readiness levels, adapting to changing market conditions and incorporating feedback from stakeholders. Regular self-assessment and improvement efforts will enhance their attractiveness to potential private funding opportunities and contribute to their long-term success. Collaboration and knowledge sharing among them will enable them to thrive their processes and learn from each other's strengths and experiences.

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Overall discussion part 1-3

In the above sections we collected inputs from the six BBECs and collected them to compare the different models. We see very different approaches to working on the BBECs and we found difficulties in comparing them directly because of these differences. The differences may occur because some centres are working across borders while others only cover one country or national region.

The differences are seen clearly in the way the centres expect to finance their activities, some centres rely highly on public funding whereas others don't plan to rely on such funding, but instead expect revenues from national and regional partners or from fees for using the centres services.

A mix of funding possibilities is preferred as to ensure not to be relying on one source of revenue. Especially for the BBECs who expect a high level of public funding it is recommended to investigate the sustainability of that model in the long term (more than 3 years), since some of the funds listed as possible contributors are based on project models for establishing centres and not for financing operations at the centre in a longer perspective.

The many public funding possibilities that have been identified are recommended to be used mainly for establishment of the centres, to develop new concepts and to ensure the communications platforms.

The self-assessment process carried out by each BBEC plays a critical role in evaluating their own investment readiness; however, it is relevant to acknowledge that this process is subjective and relies on each centre's own point of view of its performance. This subjective feature can lead to inconsistencies and discrepancies between centres, as individual interpretations, biases, or different threshold level may influence the scores assigned.

To overcome this prior statement, it is highly advisable to complement by external evaluations and feedback from stakeholders to gain a more comprehensive and objective assessment, understanding the self-assessment as a valuable starting point. Embracing diverse perspectives and seeking external validation will enable them to address potential incongruences and provide a more accurate and trustful representation of the BBEC's investment readiness level, driving them towards targeted improvement and enhancing their potential to secure private funding opportunities.

Each BBEC has provide detailed reasons of the scores for each section to ensure a valid and robust IRL, however the results might be perceived a bit overestimated, due to the current stage of their development. Mediterranean BBEC self-assessment did score lower IRL values but its behind rationale when explaining the scores represent a more realistic view of its current readiness to be invested.

The IRL for some BBECs show high degree of self confidence in finance and economic projections while others are more cautious about it. Seen from an investors point of view it may seem risky to rely on the high degree of public funding sources, since these seem to be uncertain in the long run.

It seems that the IRL levels on finance and economics does not perfectly align the financial models of all centres.

Overall, the varying levels of self-confidence in finance and economic projections within BBECs, coupled with potential uncertainties in public funding sources, highlight the complex nature of forecasting in these centres. It underscores the importance of carefully evaluating the specific characteristics and circumstances of each centre before making decisions on investments.

The landscape of funding opportunities for BBECs was developed with a deep detail level, showcasing numerous options available in the pipeline. However, setting a specific target for funding is a challenging task due to several factors, such as the changing deadlines and requirements for funding opportunities. The dynamic of these programmes can sometimes discourage the BBECs in finding the perfect match between the project funding needs and the available financing sources, resulting the public funding seeking process tougher than expected.

To overcome this issue, it is highly advisable to target local and regional opportunities in the short term, as they can provide a more straightforward and easy-to-apply experience for them. These opportunities, often tailored to the specific needs and priorities of the local community, can offer quicker evaluation processes and faster access to funds. Applying for local/regional funding not only increases the chances of securing financial support but also strengthens the BBEC's ties with the local ecosystem and enhances its relevance within the community.

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Recommendations and conclusions

At this stage of the BBEC development, drawing conclusive assessments based on sustainability can be challenging. The creation of BBECs is an iterative process that is still in its initial phase. However, it is evident that each BBEC has laid a solid foundation, which provides a promising starting point for progressing to the next level and eventually establishing a centre.

Given that the process is iterative, it implies that BBECs are continuously evolving and refining their strategies, structures, and operations. The first iteration signifies an important milestone in the development of these centres. It implies that significant progress has been made in terms of establishing the groundwork necessary for the functioning and growth of BBECs.

While conclusive sustainability assessments cannot be made at this stage, it is encouraging to note that all BBECs have taken essential steps toward building a sustainable framework. The fact that each BBEC has established a strong foundation indicates their commitment to progressing and evolving. It suggests that these centres are poised to advance to subsequent stages, where they can further refine their models, strengthen their capabilities, and enhance their overall sustainability.

However, it is important to recognize that the journey towards establishing a fully functional BBEC is ongoing. It requires continuous learning, adaptation, and collaboration to address emerging challenges and capitalize on new opportunities. As the development of BBECs proceeds, further iterations will refine and expand their scope, potentially leading to more comprehensive and robust centres in the future.

In the work ahead it is recommended to re-visit the financial models to make them as sustainable as possible and make them less repayable on funds that are based on projects in the long run.

To succeed in finding the right funding sources it is recommended to try to go for local, regional or national sources, to engage authorities and society in the existence and work of the centres. This could help the centres in finding partners, participants, and other stakeholders.

It is recommended that the self-assessment process is critically revisited in every round of development of financial model and funding possibilities, to ensure the highest level of attention on how funding and financial sustainability can affect the investment readiness level. It is advised to have external stakeholders to be part of the assessment process.

Annex 1. Templates used for data collection in part 1

BIObec task 3.3 instructions

*Explainer: According to the DoA, each local BBEC will **develop a financial plan** including the following main points:*

- *Investment plan/roadmap*
- *Cash finance needed for the start*
- *Capital costs*
- *Cash flow*
- *Profit/loss statement*

*In addition, we shall identify local/regional/national **additional funding sources** and describe innovative business model strategies concerning access to resources including*

- *Detailed plan for funding from external sources*
- *Screening of public funding sources*
- *Assessment of Investment readiness level*
- *Quantitative and qualitative aspects (markets, talents, technology landscape, economic projections)*
- *Risk and sustainability changes*

We cannot collect the info in questionnaires as the local conditions and BBEC structures will vary considerably. Probably, the most meaningful way is to describe the coming financial plan in prose, following the headlines below. In other cases (or in combination with the prose), it is possible to fill in/develop further the attached excel file and explain from that the headlines below.

In any case, we expect

1. ***a few pages (3-10 pages, including diagrams, tables etc.) for each BBEC by the end of March 2023 using the structure below***
2. ***Preliminary oral presentation at the plenary meeting in Seville, January 25-26 :***

Realistic budget and financial plan for each of the six BBecs

1. Necessary investments
 - a. Capital expenditures needed for starting (Capex)
 - b. Prepare a detailed plan
2. Operational expenses – OPEX
 - a. Teachers
 - b. Buildings
 - c. Management and Administration
 - d. Marketing/website
3. Revenues
 - a. Public funding
 - b. Participants payments
4. Cash flow – including timing
 - a. Annual input/output
 - b. Long term Financial sustainability
5. Additional Funding

The accompanying excel sheet had the following sheets

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
1	Biobec Task 3.3- Economic requirements for Biobecs						
2	Your regional BioBEC						
3	This is a framework/rough inspirational model to use for your particular BioBEC case						Notes
4							
5	Investment budget, depending on ownership/governance			€			be as specific
6		buildings (if needed)					
7		other facilities (please specify)					
8		concept development					
9		website					
10		admin					
11		other (add more lines if needed)					
12		sum					
13	Operational budget (depending on the # and type of courses)						
14		salaries					
15		Project manager 3 years, workshops					
16		teachers at courses					
17		rentals for office					
18		rental for auditorium					
19		Bbec and course marketing					
20		sum					
21	Income (depending on the # and type of courses)						
22		public support (Municipality, region, state)					
23		Municipality					
24		region					
25		state					
26		participants fee					
27		Membership fee					
28		sum					
29							
30							
31							
32							
33							
34							
35							
36							

	Name	Region coverage	Field focus	Funding details	Additional relevant information
1					
2		<i>(National/regional)</i>	<i>(e.g. Size or types of companies, sectors)</i>	<i>(e.g. Loan, guarantee, equity/venture capital)</i>	<i>(e.g. links)</i>
3					
4					
5					
6					
7					
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	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N
1	Cash Flow/Liquidity budget, monthly													
2			m1	m2	m3	m4	m5	m6	m7	m8	m9	m10	m11	m12
3														
4	CAPEX													
5		specify....												
6														
7	Opex													
8		specify....												
9														
10	Revenue													
11		specify....												
12														
13														
14														
15	Balance													
16														
17														
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Annex 2 Realistic budget and financial plan for each of the six BBecs

BBEC Central Eastern Europe

Necessary investments

The BBEC CE will act to raise awareness about bioeconomy in the Central - Eastern European region, develop education offer in this area, enhance and facilitate the cooperation between various regional actors with particular emphasis on cooperation between industry and science. The activities of the centre will be flexible enough to take advantage of the opportunities arising from regional dynamics and on the scale of the European Union. This is justified by the fact that individual countries in Central - Eastern Europe have their own specializations in bioeconomy, the level of economic development and socio-cultural conditions yet majority of them do not dispose of a national bioeconomy strategy as bioeconomy is sadly not a political priority of these countries. This generates many barriers, challenges and opportunities that can be comprehensively solved. This can be achieved only through flexible action on many levels (European, regional, national).

Investment budget, depending on ownership/governance	€
On-line platform	15 000
website	5 000
Communication materials	17 500
Office space modernization	100 000
IT hardware	35 000
IT software	35 000
Hybrid event hardware	30 000
Conference materials	7 500
sum	245 000

The developed investment plan reflects the challenges faced by BBEC CE. Activities to raise awareness and to support contacts between science and industry require the provision of professional equipment tools to facilitate contacts between key stakeholders.

On-line platform - It will be necessary to develop a dedicated platform for the exchange of knowledge between stakeholders included in the BBEC CE network. Members will gain access to a space to support contacts with other entities, obtain information about cooperation opportunities, organization of internships, offers of courses in the field of bioeconomy. It will also be a place where calls for external funding and offers to join consortia will be published.

Website - A dedicated website will be developed, which will be a communication channel for the environment and for bioeconomy actors from the region. It will contain i.a. news from the activities of BBEC CE, publications of partners and members aimed at disseminating knowledge about bioeconomy, articles. It will also provide access to databases developed by BBEC CE (education and training providers in bioeconomy, exchange programs, international mobility, internships and practices for students and science staff).

Communication materials - One of the main activities of BBEC CE will be raising awareness in the region about bioeconomy. This will cover very different levels: from basic to advanced specialized information. In addition, they will be targeted at different groups. As part of these investments, leaflets, brochures, folders, roll-ups and posters will be financed.

Office space modernization - In its activities, BBEC CE will support the exchange of knowledge, networking, and connecting scientific and industrial partners for joint educational projects in the field of bioeconomy. For this purpose, modernization works of the current office space will be carried out at the partners' premises aimed at providing a professional meetings hall for stakeholders and partners.

IT hardware, IT software, Hybrid event hardware – Those investments will be an essential element of BBEC CE equipment. Due to the huge development of remote and hybrid events caused by the COVID pandemic, BBEC CE operations will also use professional equipment to conduct such events. The range of BBEC CE covers the entire macro-region of Eastern Europe. That is why it is necessary to connect foreign partners from the region in order to share knowledge, take initiatives and conduct talks. It will be necessary to purchase laptops, professional cameras, software enabling streaming, microphones and sound system.

Conference materials - These investments will consist in the development of materials for a regional conference on bioeconomy. The issue includes welcome packs, roll-ups, posters.

Capital expenditures needed for starting (Capex)

Investment budget, depending on ownership/governance	€	YEAR 1	YEAR 2	YEAR 3	YEAR 4	YEAR 5
On-line platform	20 000,00				20 000,00	
website	5 000,00	5 000,00				
Communication materials	17 500,00	3 500,00	3500,00	3 500,00	3 500,00	3500,00
Office space modernization	100 00,00			20000,00	80 000,00	
IT hardware	35 000,00	35 000,00				
IT software	35 000,00	35 000,00				
Hybrid event hardware	30 000,00	30 000,00				
Conference materials	2 500,00	500,00	500,00	500,00	500,00	500,00
sum	245 000,00	109 000,00	4 000,00	24 000,00	104 000,00	4 000,00

The planned investments are website, communication materials, office space modernization, hardware, IT software, hybrid event hardware and conference materials. The purpose of the investments made will be to expand the network of contacts and members of BBEC CE, to create conditions for the exchange of knowledge, experience, and undertaking educational initiatives. The first year will be the most cost consuming. In the following years, investments will mainly concern communication and conference materials. There will also be investments connected to office modernization due to extending BBEC activities. In fourth year of BBEC CE's activity, it is planned to launch a dedicated on-line platform. Below is an estimated plan of investment costs for 5 years (in EUR):

Operational expenses – OPEX

Operational budget (depending on the # and type of courses)		
salaries		800 000,00
travel costs		180 000,00
IT maintenance		15 000,00
rental costs (venue for workshops and conferences)		23 500,00
catering (workshops and conferences)		26 000,00
External expertise		243 000,00
	sum	1 287 500,00
INDIRECT (25% Accounting, energy, office rental, administration Operational costs)	materials	321 875,00
	total	1 854 375,00

Operational costs are directly connected to mission and vision of BBEC CE as a bio-based education centre. The activities of BBEC CE will cover the entire macro-region of Eastern Europe and the main activities will be focused on:

1. Supporting the exchange of knowledge between the stakeholders
2. Sharing information about valuable education and training opportunities
3. Providing educational materials and expertise to raise awareness
4. Supporting cooperation between science and industry
5. Management and cooperation between the BBECs and other initiatives

Teachers/External expertise

	€	YEAR 1	YEAR 2	YEAR 3	YEAR 4	YEAR 5
External expertise	243 000,00	70 000,00	47 000,00	47 000,00	42 000,00	37 000,00
Database of education and training providers in bioeconomy	54 000,00	30 000,00	6 000,00	6 000,00	6 000,00	6 000,00
Data base about exchange programs, international mobility, internships and practices for students and science staff	39 000,00	15 000,00	6 000,00	6 000,00	6 000,00	6 000,00
Developing tools and materials to raise awareness and basic and also advanced knowledge about the bioeconomy	50 000,00	5 000,00	15 000,00	15 000,00	10 000,00	5 000,00
Mapping the regional needs to provide tailored made educational and training curricula	100 000,00	20 000,00	20 000,00	20 000,00	20 000,00	20 000,00

1. BBEC will engage external experts (mainly from the world of science and academia) **to develop tailored made educational training curricula**. This activity is related to mapping industry needs in terms of dedicated training within Key activity nr 4. BBEC as an institution

will not conduct training with its own staff. Training for the industry will be carried out by scientific partners and IRWG. It is estimated that EUR 100,000.00 per 5 years will be allocated for this purpose.

2. BBEC CE will disseminate information about current educational opportunities in the macro-region. Thanks to the involvement of our own staff and external experts, **two databases will be created:**

- Database of education and training providers in bioeconomy
- Database about exchange programs, international mobility, internships and practices for students and science staff

It is estimated that EUR 45.000,00 will be allocated for this purpose. The databases will be continuously updated every 2 months. The estimated cost is 12.000,00 EUR per year.

3. Regarding the Key Activity 3, teachers and external experts will also be engaged to develop tools and **materials to raise awareness and basic and also advanced knowledge** about the bioeconomy: informational brochures, manuals, lesson plans, short videos and others. It is estimated that EUR 50,000.00 will be allocated for this purpose.

Buildings / Venues

	€	YEAR 1	YEAR 2	YEAR 3	YEAR 4	YEAR 5
rental costs (venue for workshops and conferences)	23 500,00	4 700,00	4 700,00	4 700,00	4 700,00	4 700,00
catering (workshops and conferences)	26 000,00	5 200,00	5 200,00	5 200,00	5 200,00	5 200,00

The costs of renting the BBEC coordinating offices are collectively included in indirect costs. However, the costs of renting training and conference rooms for the organization of workshops (small events) and conferences on bioeconomy in the region were provided.

Workshops (small events) will be physical meetings for max. 15 participants dedicated to:

- Meetings for the members of BBEC (stakeholders group, working groups, networking)
- Meetings with potential new members of BBEC
- Matchmaking events for start-ups and industry
- Matchmaking events for science staff, students and industry
- Events promoting bioeconomy and BBEC

The cost of renting a room for 15 participants is estimated at 500 EUR. The cost of catering for 15 participants is estimated at 400 EUR. It is planned to organize 8 smaller events per year.

Conference will be physical meetings for max. 80 participants dedicated to:

- Promoting bioeconomy in the region and valuable educations offers
- Promoting achievements of BBEC CE and other BBEC's
- Engaging potential new members, networking
- Promoting exchange programs, international mobility, internships and practices for students and science staff

The cost of renting a room for 80 participants is estimated at EUR 700,00. The cost of catering for 15 participants is estimated at 2000 EUR. It is planned to organize 1 conference per year.

During 5 years estimated costs of renting a venue for 40 workshops and 5 conference is 23.500,00 EUR. The costs of catering 26.000,00 EUR.

Management and Admin

		€	YEAR 1	YEAR 2	YEAR 3	YEAR 4	YEAR 5
salaries	800 000,00		140 000,00	140 000,00	140 000,00	160 000,00	220 000,00
Coordination of BBEC	700 000,00		120 000,00	120 000,00	120 000,00	140 000,00	200 000,00
Application for funds	100 000,00		20 000,00	20 000,00	20 000,00	20 000,00	20 000,00
travel costs	180 000,00		36 000,00				
BBEC coordinators	60 000,00		12 000,00	12 000,00	12 000,00	12 000,00	12 000,00
refund participants of workshops	120 000,00		24 000,00	24 000,00	24 000,00	24 000,00	24 000,00
IT maintenance	15 000,00		3 000,00				

INDIRECT COSTS (25%):							
Accounting, energy, office rental, administration materials	321 875,00	64 725,00	58 975,00	58 975,00	62 725,00	76 475,00	

Coordination of BBEC, estimated cost of internal staff: 10.000,00 EUR per month, 120.000,00 EUR per year.

From year 4, it is planned to increase employment due to the development of BBEC CE activities. That is why the salaries increases in year 4 and 5. Number of full time staff will increase from 3 in year 1 to 5 in year 5.

Key involvement of internal staff includes:

- meetings with the Steering Committee, Stakeholders Groups and Working Groups
- coordination activities
- communicating with other BBECs
- IT maintenance (website, platform)
- developing communication materials
- social media and other channels
- participating in conferences, events, meetings
- updating website

Application for funds, estimated cost of internal staff: 20.000,00 EUR per year. It is estimated that this amount of effort will be appropriate to write 4 applications for external funds for BBEC CE development.

Travel costs are connected to management and administration. Staff of the BBEC CE will participate in various events, meetings with other BBEC's and stakeholders. Monthly travel budget is estimated for 1.000,00 EUR (12.000,00 EUR/year).

Travel costs also consists a refund to participants of workshops for their travel expenses. It is planned that there will be 200 EUR/participant. 8 workshops per year with 15 participants each sums to 24.000,00 EUR per year.

IT maintenance connected to managing the BBEC CE website, support for hybrid events, IT service is estimated at 250 EUR per month.

Indirect costs consists among others accounting, energy, office rental, administration materials. They will constitute 25% of other direct costs mentioned above.

Revenues

	€	YEAR 1	YEAR 2	YEAR 3	YEAR 4	YEAR 5
External funding	1 872 918,75	436 951,25	301 863,75	322 063,75	421 801,25	390 238,75
Membership fee	125 000,00					125 000,00
Tailored-made curricula for the industry	100 000,00					100 000,00
Access to an online platform	50 000,00					50 000,00
Other services provided by the BBEC	20 000,00					20 000,00
sum	2 167 918,75	436 951,25	301 863,75	322 063,75	421 801,25	685 238,75

Public funding

It is planned to rely on external funding for the first years of the BBEC CE initiative. A detailed analysis of potential funding sources will be included in the "Additional funding" table.

Membership fee

From year 5, there are plans to introduce fees for BBEC CE affiliated members. The first four years of activity will be aimed at a thorough examination of the needs, building partners' capacity and connecting them. In this way, a value will be generated thanks to which partners will want to pay membership fees. Due to the different types of stakeholders, it is estimated that the average annual contribution will be EUR 2,500/year. In the first year, it is estimated that 50 permanent partners will be acquired. This is an ambitious goal, but taking into account the scope of the entire macro-region, it is realistic.

Tailored made curricula for the industry

It is estimated that during year 5 we will be able to contract 20 entities to develop for them tailored made curricula and training programs. The estimated prices for one programme/curriculum will be 5 000 EUR.

Access to on-line platform

It is estimated that during year 5 we will be able to contract 250 entities for payments 200 EUR/year for the access to developed on-line platform.

Other service provided by the BBEC

At this stage, we do not want to pinpoint other potential services provided by BBEC CE. The amount of EUR 20,000/year was accepted as remuneration for the preparation of external funding applications for external entities.

Cash flow – in the short and long term

Cash flow year 1

Item	m1	m2	m3	m4	m5	m6	m7	m8	m9	m10	m11	m12
CAPEX	0,00	103 500,00	5 000,00	0,00	0,00	500,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
On-line platform website			5 000,00									
Communication materials		3 500,00										
Office space modernization												
IT hardware		35 000,00										
IT software		35 000,00										
Hybrid event hardware		30 000,00										
Conference materials						500,00						
Opex	18 645,84	20 192,71	20 192,71	20 192,71	20 192,71	82 692,71	18 645,84	18 645,84	20 192,71	45 192,71	20 192,71	18 645,84
salaries	11 666,67	11 666,67	11 666,67	11 666,67	11 666,67	11 666,67	11 666,67	11 666,67	11 666,67	11 666,67	11 666,67	11 666,67
travel costs	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00
IT maintenance	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00
rental costs (venue for workshops and conferences)		587,50	587,50	587,50	587,50	587,50			587,50	587,50	587,50	
catering (workshops and conferences)		650,00	650,00	650,00	650,00	650,00			650,00	650,00	650,00	
External expertise						50 000,00				20 000,00		
INDIRECT (25%)	3 729,17	4 038,54	4 038,54	4 038,54	4 038,54	16 538,54	3 729,17	3 729,17	4 038,54	9 038,54	4 038,54	3 729,17
Revenue	18 832,30	124 929,64	25 444,64	20 394,64	20 394,64	84 024,64	18 832,30	18 832,30	20 394,64	45 644,64	20 394,64	18 832,30
External funding	18 832,30	124 929,64	25 444,64	20 394,64	20 394,64	84 024,64	18 832,30	18 832,30	20 394,64	45 644,64	20 394,64	18 832,30
Membership fee												
Tailored made curriculars for the industry												
Access to on-line platform												
Other service provided by the BBEC												
Total net cash flows	186,46	1 236,93	251,93	201,93	201,93	831,93	186,46	186,46	201,93	451,93	201,93	186,46
Cash opening balance	0,00	186,46	1 423,39	1 675,32	1 877,25	2 079,18	2 911,11	3 097,57	3 284,03	3 485,96	3 937,89	4 139,82
Closing balance of cash	186,46	1 423,39	1 675,32	1 877,25	2 079,18	2 911,11	3 097,57	3 284,03	3 485,96	3 937,89	4 139,82	4 326,28

Item	m1	m2	m3	m4	m5	m6	m7	m8	m9	m10	m11	m12
CAPEX	0,00	3 500,00	0,00	0,00	500,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
On-line platform website												
Communication materials		3 500,00										
Office space modernization												
IT hardware												
IT software												
Hybrid event hardware												
Conference materials					500,00							
Opex	18 645,84	22 692,71	20 192,71	22 692,71	38 942,71	22 692,71	18 645,84	21 145,84	45 192,71	22 692,71	20 192,71	21 145,84
salaries	11 666,67	11 666,67	11 666,67	11 666,67	11 666,67	11 666,67	11 666,67	11 666,67	11 666,67	11 666,67	11 666,67	11 666,67
travel costs	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00
IT maintenance	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00
rental costs (venue for workshops and conferences)		587,50	587,50	587,50	587,50	587,50			587,50	587,50	587,50	
catering (workshops and conferences)		650,00	650,00	650,00	650,00	650,00			650,00	650,00	650,00	
External expertise		2 000,00	2 000,00	2 000,00	15 000,00	2 000,00		2 000,00	20 000,00	2 000,00		2 000,00
INDIRECT (25%)	3 729,17	4 538,54	4 038,54	4 538,54	7 788,54	4 538,54	3 729,17	4 229,17	9 038,54	4 538,54	4 038,54	4 229,17
Revenue	18 832,30	26 454,64	20 394,64	22 919,64	39 837,14	22 919,64	18 832,30	21 357,30	45 644,64	22 919,64	20 394,64	21 357,30
External funding	18 832,30	26 454,64	20 394,64	22 919,64	39 837,14	22 919,64	18 832,30	21 357,30	45 644,64	22 919,64	20 394,64	21 357,30
Membership fee												
Tailored made curriculars for the industry												
Access to on-line platform												
Other service provided by the BBEC												
Total net cash flows	186,46	261,93	201,93	226,93	394,43	226,93	186,46	211,46	451,93	226,93	201,93	211,46
Cash opening balance	4 326,28	4 512,74	4 774,67	4 976,60	5 203,53	5 597,96	5 824,89	6 011,35	6 222,81	6 674,74	6 901,67	7 103,60
Closing balance of cash	4 512,74	4 774,67	4 976,60	5 203,53	5 597,96	5 824,89	6 011,35	6 222,81	6 674,74	6 901,67	7 103,60	7 315,06

Cash flow year 2

Cash flow year 3

Cash flow

Item	m1	m2	m3	m4	m5	m6	m7	m8	m9	m10	m11	m12
CAPEX	0,00	3 500,00	0,00	0,00	500,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	20 000,00	0,00	0,00
On-line platform website												
Communication materials		3 500,00										
Office space modernization										20 000,00		
IT hardware												
IT software												
Hybrid event hardware												
Conference materials					500,00							
Opex	18 645,84	22 692,71	20 192,71	22 692,71	38 942,71	22 692,71	18 645,84	21 145,84	45 192,71	22 692,71	20 192,71	21 145,84
salaries	11 666,67	11 666,67	11 666,67	11 666,67	11 666,67	11 666,67	11 666,67	11 666,67	11 666,67	11 666,67	11 666,67	11 666,67
travel costs	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00
IT maintenance	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00
rental costs (venue for workshops and conferences)		587,50	587,50	587,50	587,50	587,50			587,50	587,50	587,50	587,50
catering (workshops and conferences)		650,00	650,00	650,00	650,00	650,00			650,00	650,00	650,00	
External expertise		2 000,00		2 000,00	15 000,00	2 000,00		2 000,00	20 000,00	2 000,00		2 000,00
INDIRECT (25%)	3 729,17	4 538,54	4 038,54	4 538,54	7 788,54	4 538,54	3 729,17	4 229,17	9 038,54	4 538,54	4 038,54	4 229,17
Revenue	18 832,30	26 454,64	20 394,64	22 919,64	39 837,14	22 919,64	18 832,30	21 357,30	45 644,64	43 119,64	20 394,64	21 357,30
External funding	18 832,30	26 454,64	20 394,64	22 919,64	39 837,14	22 919,64	18 832,30	21 357,30	45 644,64	43 119,64	20 394,64	21 357,30
Membership fee												
Tailored made curricula for the industry												
Access to on-line platform												
Other service provided by the BBEC												
Total net cash flows	186,46	261,93	201,93	226,93	394,43	226,93	186,46	211,46	451,93	426,93	201,93	211,46
Cash opening balance	7 315,06	7 501,52	7 763,45	7 965,38	8 192,31	8 586,74	8 813,67	9 000,13	9 211,59	9 663,52	10 090,45	10 292,38
Closing balance of cash	7 501,52	7 763,45	7 965,38	8 192,31	8 586,74	8 813,67	9 000,13	9 211,59	9 663,52	10 090,45	10 292,38	10 503,84

year 4

Item	m1	m2	m3	m4	m5	m6	m7	m8	m9	m10	m11	m12
CAPEX	0,00	3 500,00	40 000,00	0,00	500,00	20 000,00	20 000,00	0,00	0,00	20 000,00	0,00	0,00
On-line platform website							20 000,00					
Communication materials		3 500,00										
Office space modernization			40 000,00			20 000,00				20 000,00		
IT hardware												
IT software												
Hybrid event hardware												
Conference materials					500,00							
Opex	20 729,16	24 776,04	22 276,04	24 776,04	34 776,04	24 776,04	20 729,16	23 229,16	47 276,04	24 776,04	22 276,04	23 229,16
salaries	13 333,33	13 333,33	13 333,33	13 333,33	13 333,33	13 333,33	13 333,33	13 333,33	13 333,33	13 333,33	13 333,33	13 333,33
travel costs	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00
IT maintenance	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00
rental costs (venue for workshops and conferences)		587,50	587,50	587,50	587,50	587,50			587,50	587,50	587,50	587,50
catering (workshops and conferences)		650,00	650,00	650,00	650,00	650,00			650,00	650,00	650,00	
External expertise		2 000,00		2 000,00	10 000,00	2 000,00		2 000,00	20 000,00	2 000,00		2 000,00
INDIRECT (25%)	4 145,83	4 955,21	4 455,21	4 955,21	6 955,21	4 955,21	4 145,83	4 645,83	9 455,21	4 955,21	4 455,21	4 645,83
Revenue	20 936,45	28 558,80	62 898,80	25 023,80	35 628,80	45 223,80	41 136,45	23 461,45	47 748,80	45 223,80	22 498,80	23 461,45
External funding	20 936,45	28 558,80	62 898,80	25 023,80	35 628,80	45 223,80	41 136,45	23 461,45	47 748,80	45 223,80	22 498,80	23 461,45
Membership fee												
Tailored made curricula for the industry												
Access to on-line platform												
Other service provided by the BBEC												
Total net cash flows	207,29	282,76	622,76	247,76	352,76	447,76	407,29	232,29	472,76	447,76	222,76	232,29
Cash opening balance	10 503,84	10 711,13	10 993,89	11 616,65	11 864,41	12 217,17	12 664,93	13 072,22	13 304,51	13 777,27	14 225,03	14 447,79
Closing balance of cash	10 711,13	10 993,89	11 616,65	11 864,41	12 217,17	12 664,93	13 072,22	13 304,51	13 777,27	14 225,03	14 447,79	14 680,08

Cash flow year 5

Item	m1	m2	m3	m4	m5	m6	m7	m8	m9	m10	m11	m12
CAPEX	0,00	3 500,00	0,00	0,00	500,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
On-line platform website												
Communication materials		3 500,00										
Office space modernization												
IT hardware												
IT software												
Hybrid event hardware												
Conference materials					500,00							
Opex	26 979,16	31 026,04	28 526,04	31 026,04	34 776,04	31 026,04	26 979,16	29 479,16	53 526,04	31 026,04	28 526,04	29 479,16
salaries	18 333,33	18 333,33	18 333,33	18 333,33	18 333,33	18 333,33	18 333,33	18 333,33	18 333,33	18 333,33	18 333,33	18 333,33
travel costs	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00	3 000,00
IT maintenance	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00	250,00
rental costs (venue for workshops and conferences)		587,50	587,50	587,50	587,50	587,50			587,50	587,50	587,50	
catering (workshops and conferences)		650,00	650,00	650,00	650,00	650,00			650,00	650,00	650,00	
External expertise		2 000,00		2 000,00	5 000,00	2 000,00		2 000,00	20 000,00	2 000,00		2 000,00
INDIRECT (25%)	5 395,83	6 205,21	5 705,21	6 205,21	6 955,21	6 205,21	5 395,83	5 895,83	10 705,21	6 205,21	5 705,21	5 895,83
Revenue	69 332,29	76 954,64	60 894,64	53 419,64	57 712,14	53 419,64	39 332,29	41 857,29	76 144,64	53 419,64	50 894,64	51 857,29
External funding	27 248,95	34 871,30	28 811,30	31 336,30	35 628,80	31 336,30	27 248,95	29 773,95	54 061,30	31 336,30	28 811,30	29 773,95
Membership fee	10 416,67	10 416,67	10 416,67	10 416,67	10 416,67	10 416,67	10 416,67	10 416,67	10 416,67	10 416,67	10 416,67	10 416,67
Tailored made curricula for the industry	10 000,00	10 000,00	10 000,00	10 000,00	10 000,00	10 000,00			10 000,00	10 000,00	10 000,00	10 000,00
Access to on-line platform	20 000,00	20 000,00	10 000,00									
Other service provided by the BBEC	1 666,67	1 666,67	1 666,67	1 666,67	1 666,67	1 666,67	1 666,67	1 666,67	1 666,67	1 666,67	1 666,67	1 666,67
Total net cash flows	42 353,13	42 428,60	32 368,60	22 393,60	22 436,10	22 393,60	12 353,13	12 378,13	22 618,60	22 393,60	22 368,60	22 378,13
Cash opening balance	14 680,08	57 033,21	99 461,81	131 830,41	154 224,01	176 660,11	199 053,71	211 406,84	223 784,97	246 403,57	268 797,17	291 165,77
Closing balance of cash	57 033,21	99 461,81	131 830,41	154 224,01	176 660,11	199 053,71	211 406,84	223 784,97	246 403,57	268 797,17	291 165,77	313 543,90

Financial sustainability assessment

It is planned that financing of activities in the pilot period will be secured from external funds. Public funding will help maintain the financial stability of the BBEC CE. They will be used to develop a network of relevant stakeholders, support the cooperation and raise awareness in the region in order to provide valuable educational offers on a commercial basis in year 5 of operation. Considering the large number of sources of potential external financing this is a reasonable and realistic assumption. It has to be underlined that the idea of BBEC also goes in line with the policy of regional development in the field of bioeconomy. This factor will also additionally ensure the stability of financing the project. The leader of BBEC CE - PRO CIVIS is an active entity which currently implements a number of projects. PRO CIVIS will be able to provide financial liquidity from its own funds, if necessary. If necessary, PRO CIVIS can count on financial support from its Founders and other commercial entities with whom he interacts on a daily basis.

Finnish BBEC: GreenHub

Necessary investments

Investment budget, depending on ownership/governance		€
	Concept development: materials for platform (pictures, videos etc.), key actors	15 000
	Online platform	15 000
	Administration	5 000
	other (add more lines if needed)	
	sum	35 000

Capital expenditures needed for starting (Capex)

The Finnish BBEC functions as an online collaboration and innovation platform. Hence, the main investment relates to setting up an online platform. This would cost approximately 15 000 € if an outside website developer was used and specific functionalities were to obtain as well as website/domain licenses for some years forward. The concept development in the beginning would cost an additional 15 000 € through which social media, communications and marketing practices would be set up and key actor meetings would be organized. Here also 5 000€ would be dedicated to administrative costs including organization and planning of the first-year activities.

All the appliances needed e.g., laptop and mobilephone, would be provided by the platform coordinator organization and hence they are not included in the CAPEX.

Operational expenses – OPEX

One year operational budget (depending on the # and type of courses)		
	salaries	
	Coordinator of the platform	65 000
	"Hubber" from each organisation	80 000
	BBEC platform marketing & communications	6 000
	sum	151 000

BBEC activities including e.g., joint lectures or courses will be financed by the key actors themselves and no operational expenses are directed here.

Teachers

No expenses are derived from teaching since this is provided through the key actors and some expenses are dedicated to the key actor organisations in terms of management.

Buildings

No physical buildings are needed for the BBEC. The coordinator of the BBEC will work in the premises of Business Joensuu or other coordinator organization. The rents for spaces in each key actor organization for specific staff working with the BBEC as well as the coordinator will be included in the management and admin expenses.

Management and Admin

The operational expenses needed for the BBEC include salary for the BBEC platform coordinator. This would be an expert/senior level position and thus the salary would range from 5500-6500 €/month (including insurance and other employment costs) depending on the person's previous experience and educational background. In addition, an additional 10 000€/year/key actor would be required for active participation in the BBEC (in total 80 000€/per year), especially dedicated to the salaries of the staff.

Marketing/communications

Marketing and communication costs including production of videos, pictures, and other social media activity, would cost approximately 6 000 €/year.

Revenues

Income		
	public support (Municipality, region, state)	
	City of Joensuu	
	Regional council of North Karelia	
	state	
	Key actor participation/year	101 000
	Services provided	50 000
	sum	151 000

Revenues gained from services provided through BBEC are directed to the key actor involved directly. For instance, one of the key actors Natural Resources Institute (Luke) offers a service called "Rent a genius" through which researchers are hired to companies to work on a specific issue. The customer company directly pays Luke for this service and the BBEC platform is there just to provide information on the service and connect the involved actors – Luke and the company. With regards to educational services, e.g., the thesis work offered by the BSc and MSc level students, the company involved pays directly the student for the thesis work. Here, the platform again functions as the collaboration platform for the students and companies to get involved. These revenues are estimated worth of 50 000€/year.

The Finnish BBEC is not a limited company, and it functions under the coordinator organization. And hence no money is transferred through the BBEC. Although, in the future the BBEC could be a spin-off.

Public funding

Some public funding e.g., from regional innovation/development fund, could be applied for developing the platform. The applied sum would be approx. 150-300 000 €. Several key actors could be part of applying the fund while majority would be directed to the coordination and development of the BBEC.

Participants payments

Revenues are expected to derive from the key actors' participation in the BBEC. This would be approximately 10-15 000€/year/key actor.

Furthermore, in the future more participant payments could be derived from local companies.

Cash flow – in the short and long term

The main difference in the cash flows between the first and years proceeding is that there is the main investment for the online platform during the first year as well as some administrative and concept development costs. After the first years, the costs relate to operational expenses whereas incomes derive from key actor participation costs and services provided.

Cash flow year 1

Cash Flow/Liquidity budget, monthly	m1	m2	m3	m4	m5	m6	m7	m8	m9	m10	m11	m12	Year in tota
CAPEX													
Platform development	0	0	0	-14500	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Website/domain licences	0	0	0	-500	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Administrative costs	0	0	0	0	0	-2500	0	0	0	0	0	0	-2500
Concept development	0	-5000	0	0	0	0	-5000	0	0	0	0	-5000	0
Opex													
Salary of the coordinator	-6000	-6000	-6000	-6000	-6000	-6000	-6000	-6000	-6000	-6000	-6000	-6000	-6000
Marketing and communication	-500	-500	-500	-500	-500	-500	-500	-500	-500	-500	-500	-500	-500
Costs for key actor participation	-6700	-6700	-6700	-6700	-6700	-6700	-6700	-6700	-6700	-6700	-6700	-6700	-6700
Revenue													
Key actor participation	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	11000
Services provided through the BBEC	0	0	5000	5000	5000	5000	5000	5000	5000	5000	5000	5000	5000
Balance	4000	-1000	4000	-11000	4000	1500	-1000	4000	4000	4000	-1000	2500	14000

Cash flow year 2

Cash Flow/Liquidity budget, monthly	m1	m2	m3	m4	m5	m6	m7	m8	m9	m10	m11	m12	Year in tota
CAPEX													
Platform development	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Website/domain licences	0	0	0	-500	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Administrative costs	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Concept development	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Opex													
Salary of the coordinator	-6000	-6000	-6000	-6000	-6000	-6000	-6000	-6000	-6000	-6000	-6000	-6000	-6000
Marketing and communication	-500	-500	-500	-500	-500	-500	-500	-500	-500	-500	-500	-500	-500
Costs for key actor participation	-6700	-6700	-6700	-6700	-6700	-6700	-6700	-6700	-6700	-6700	-6700	-6700	-6700
Revenue													
Key actor participation	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	11000
Services provided through the BBEC	0	0	5000	5000	5000	5000	5000	5000	5000	5000	5000	5000	5000
Balance	4000	4000	4000	3500	4000	5000	48500						

Financial sustainability assessment

To support the financial stability and future sustainability of the BBEC, the aim is to gain funding from sources outside project funding. The main funding would be dedicated to managing the collaboration platform and hence the expenses would stay rather small. For this, one jointly funded employee is needed as “a collaboration coordinator” and no additional employees are required. Within five years' time, the goal is to gain most revenues from the offered services and keep the participation fees

lower. In practice this would mean that the participation fee would be approximately 50k € and income gained from services would be 100k €.

This project has received funding from the Bio-based Industries Joint Undertaking (JU) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101023381. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the Bio-based Industries Consortium.

German BBEC

Necessary investments

As specified in the governance plan, the German BBEC will be part of the University of Hohenheim and it will be located in the campus of the university. The main investments so the BBEC can work independently will have to cover:

1. Salaries of two persons for one year
2. Two laptops and additional devices (mouse, extra screen, keyboard, printer, docking station)
3. Office supplies for one year

The following investments can potentially be covered by the university/ Bioeconomy office:

1. Office(s) and its maintenance
2. Furniture and office equipment (phone line, internet connection, lighting,)
3. University services: administration, IT, web hosting
4. Secretary salary for BBEC-related activities
5. Software licenses
6. Advise and/or services on topics such as procurement, data management, ethics, occupational safety, meeting rooms, human resources management, sports options for employees, among others, marketing and communication through the university social media and website channels.

Capital expenditures needed for starting (Capex)

<i>Item</i>	<i>Cost (euros)</i>
Salaries of two persons for one year (TVL 13, Stufe 3)	120.000
Four laptops and additional devices (mouse, extra screen, keyboard, printer, docking station)	7.000
Office supplies for one year	1.000
Travel and other expenses to build a first package of services for the three Workstreams (communication + network + products + projects)	5.000
Total	133.000

Covered by the university:

<i>Items (for one year)</i>	<i>Cost (euros)</i>
Office(s) and its maintenance	3.000
Furniture and office equipment (phone line, internet connection, lighting,)	600
University services: administration, IT, web hosting	50
Secretary salary for BBEC-related activities (10%)	5.000
Software licenses for four laptops	240
Advise and/or services on topics such as procurement, data management, ethics, occupational safety, meeting rooms, human resources management, sports options for employees, among others, marketing and communication through the university social media and website channels	-

Detailed investment plan

Operational expenses – OPEX

The operational expenses depend on the on-demand activities based on the work streams defined in the governance structure:

- Communication activities
- Network activities
- Projects
- Products:
 - o Courses development
 - o Courses adaptation/ creation - consultancy service
 - o Marketing of offerings

Salaries:

To calculate the expenses, the unit is the cost of the hour. For effects of the calculation, an exemplary employee with TVL 13, Stufe 3 is considered. The cost per hour is 30 euros/hour.

Travel expenses:

Per diem:

Type and Time	Cost (euros)
---------------	--------------

Domestic travel and more than 8 hours or more	6
Domestic travel and more than 14 hours or more	12
Domestic travel and more than 24 hours or more	24
Abroad travel and more than 8 hours or more	40% of the foreign per diem
Abroad travel and more than 14 hours or more	80% of the foreign per diem
Abroad travel and more than 24 hours or more	100% of the foreign per diem

Fees for foreign per diem and lodging allowance depend on the country. Following the university's rules, there could be some reductions in case of meals included in the program.

Lodging allowance:

The traveler will receive a lodging allowance for business trips which last for multiple calendar days and are at least 12 hours long. The allowances will follow the university's rules and it ranges from 20-120 euros per day depending on context.

Travel expenses:

Depending on the price of the train/ flight/bus ticket. When the private car or bike is used, there is a reimbursement of 0.25-0.35 euro/km

Marketing expenses:

On demand:

Posters: 5-10 euros/poster

PVC banner: 20 euros

Flyers: 10 euros/100 flyers

Cards: 5 euros/50 cards

Office Supplies:

We believe that office supplies do not need to be high. However, we estimate 1.000 euros for office supplies (pens, pencils, markers, highlighters, paper clips, paper, tape, etc.) per year or 83 euros per month.

Online collaboration tools:

This budget includes online collaboration tools such as Miro. Costs ranges from 8-16 euros per member per month. Considering the 4 members of the team and 2-3 tools, we can calculate an approximate cost of 150 euros per month.

Rooms/ space:

For courses or events, we expect to use the facilities of the university

External experts' fees:

Depending on the activity and the expert we have calculated external experts' fees of three classes:

Expert type	Cost (Euros/hour)
Consultant, Master, Phd (internal or external)	40-70
Internal professor, senior consultant	70-100
External expert	90-150

The final cost will be calculated multiplying the cost by hours of consultancy or teaching/coaching.

Events expenses:

Item	Cost
External venue rental	1000-5000 euros depending on size and services

Food and beverages	30 euros/participant
Marketing/promotion	See marketing expenses
Salaries for planners	30 euros/hour
Staff	13-22 euros/ hour
Experts	See External experts' fees

The event planning will have to consider specific costs depending on the event goals and scope.

Revenues

Funding sources

Based on the defined governance structure, charging directly for services and products is not possible because the BBEC will be part of the public body University of Hohenheim. Then, for the German BBEC, we predict that we will obtain in-kind contributions from the University of Hohenheim and budget for the first year from public funding programs from the ministries of the state of Baden Württemberg.

In the following years, an important income source will be the projects at regional, national and international level:

BW calls

- Project examples:
 - Ideenwettbewerb Bioökonomie 2023
 - Spitze auf den Land!. Technologieführer (ELR)
 - Bioökonomie Innovations- und Investitionsprogramm für den Ländlichen Raum
 - Netzwerkiniciativen zur Weiterentwicklung der Leitregion Nachhaltige Bioökonomie
 - Struktur- und Innovationsfonds für die Forschung (SI-BW)
 - InnovationChallenge – Nachhaltige Produktion und Mobilität
 - Holz innovative Programm
 - Individual funding programs
 - Margarete von Wrangell-Programm
 - Mathilde-Planck-Lehrauftragsprogramm
 - MuT-Mentoring und Training

German calls

- Funding possibilities:
- The research funding of the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) in the field of bioeconomy e.g. Bioeconomy International
- Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture
- Nationale-stadtentwicklungspolitik

European calls

- Horizon Europe
- Erasmus+
- LIFE
- European Regional Development Fund (ERDF)
- Interreg calls

Participants payments

In general, the rules and nature of the BBEC do not allow to directly charge for courses. However, for some activities, we predict we can have co-financing strategies with other institutions by creating win-to-win activities. Some examples are:

- Exhibitions on Bioeconomy with the support of Experimenta
- Master courses co-created with AgroParisTech and BOKU
- Co-creation of courses for primary school, secondary school, and VET students
- Courses of continuing education with the Further development of teaching department of the University of Hohenheim

The division of the revenues depend on how involved the BBEC is in the development of the courses. This will be defined in a course-by-course basis.

Cash flow – in the short and long term

A cash flow diagram for year 1 is seen below.

Cash Flow/Liquidity budget, monthly	m1	m2	m3	m4	m5	m6	m7	m8	m9	m10	m11	m12	
CAPEX													
Laptops	4.000,00 €									3.000,00 €			
Furniture and office equipment (phon	600,00 €												
University services: administration, IT,	50,00 €												
Software licenses for four laptops	240,00 €												
Opex													
Salary 1st person	4.748,54 €	4.748,54 €	4.748,54 €	4.748,54 €	4.748,54 €	4.748,54 €	4.748,54 €	4.748,54 €	4.748,54 €	4.748,54 €	4.748,54 €	4.748,54 €	
Salary 2nd person	4.748,54 €	4.748,54 €	4.748,54 €	4.748,54 €	4.748,54 €	4.748,54 €	4.748,54 €	4.748,54 €	4.748,54 €	4.748,54 €	4.748,54 €	4.748,54 €	
Office supplies	83,33 €	83,33 €	83,33 €	83,33 €	83,33 €	83,33 €	83,33 €	83,33 €	83,33 €	83,33 €	83,33 €	83,33 €	
Travel expenses	416,67 €	416,67 €	416,67 €	416,67 €	416,67 €	416,67 €	416,67 €	416,67 €	416,67 €	416,67 €	416,67 €	416,67 €	
Office(s) and its maintenance	250,00 €	250,00 €	250,00 €	250,00 €	250,00 €	250,00 €	250,00 €	250,00 €	250,00 €	250,00 €	250,00 €	250,00 €	covered by universi
Salary secretary	416,67 €	416,67 €	416,67 €	416,67 €	416,67 €	416,67 €	416,67 €	416,67 €	416,67 €	416,67 €	416,67 €	416,67 €	covered by Bioecon
Revenue													
Funding from BW state	133.000,00 €												
Funding from University	9.000,00 €												
Balance	126.446,25 €	115.782,51 €	105.118,76 €	94.455,01 €	83.791,27 €	73.127,52 €	62.463,77 €	51.800,03 €	41.136,28 €	27.472,53 €	16.808,79 €	6.145,04 €	

Financial sustainability assessment

Irish BBEC Financial Plan

Necessary investments

Capital expenditures needed for starting (Capex)

The main form of capital expenditure for the Irish BBEC will be the website design. The website will be a key asset in the Irish BBEC providing information on all aspects of Irish bioeconomy including news, and events and disseminating information about National and European projects. The website will also host a database to provide information about the Irish bioeconomy for a range of users including researchers, government departments, primary producer sector and civic society. The website design is expected to cost €15,000.

Operational expenses – OPEX

Management and Admin

The Irish BBEC will have two full-time staff: Program Manager and a Community Manager. The total annual salaries of the staff will be €127,657.15. The two staff will have a travel budget of €5000 per year.

External Staff

There will be several external bioeconomy stakeholders providing expert mentorship in their field (technical mentorship and advisory roles on accessing financing). This is expected to cost €10,800 per year.

Buildings

The Irish BBEC will have access to Munster Technological University (MTU) Kerry campus and the National Bioeconomy Campus in Tipperary. Where additional rooms are required for hosting events these will be hired. Event room hire and catering has been budgeted at €5000 per year.

Marketing/website

The Community Manager will be responsible for the marketing of the Irish BBEC. The website will need to be regularly updated with recent events and news. The support and hosting of the website is expected to cost €2000 per year. Online collaborative tools such as Canva, Miro and Zoom have been included in the budget at €1000 per year. The data mining tool that is proposed for the talent and skills portal is budgeted at €5000 per year.

Revenues

Public funding

It is envisioned that the Irish BBEC will require grant funding. The total funding based on a 3 year operation cycle would need to be 485400€ to meet the estimated capital and operational costs as described above.

Sources of grant aid could include:

- Department of Agriculture, Food and Marine (DAFM)
- Department of Environment, Climate and Communications (DECC)
- Environmental Protection Agency (EPA)
- Enterprise Ireland
- Science Foundation Ireland

- InterTradeIreland

Participants payments

Educational courses in Ireland are largely subsidised such that the student pays a minimal administrative cost only. Additional revenue streams have been assessed and could include:

- Participation in national and EU education and skills related projects
- Income from finders fees from students funnelled into courses
- Technical Mentoring
- Bioeconomy Apprenticeships – leverage of MTU and partner organisation staff skillset to create industry coaching days
- Income from one day training & upskilling events
- Networking and Knowledge Exchange Events

Cash flow – 3 year projection

The Irish case has developed a total cost model and the cashflow models annually and for different types of courses.

Irish BBEC Cost Model		Existing Project KPI		Partners	Core Staff Member	Activities	
BBEC Offering		Existing Project KPI		Partners	Core Staff Member	Activities	
Accredited programs level 6 – 9 signposting	IKC3 / biobec	Universities	Program Manager	QQI Framework 6–10			
Schools Engagement Program	IKC3 / biobec	IKC3 / CircBio	Community Manager	Development and Delivery of program designed for school students aged 5 – 18 including schools visits			
Knowledge Exchange (Microcredentials)	IKC3/BIO/BIC/BIOBEC / IBF	Cluster Activity	Program Manager	Event organisation – 6 events per year			
Bioeconomy Accelerator / Enterprise Dev	IKC3/BIO/BIC/BIOBEC / IBF	Cluster Activity	Program Manager	Collab with Cluster on annual 2 intakes to accelerator & support on project dev, funding & finance			
Mentorship & Advisory	IKC3/BIO/BIC/BIOBEC / IBF	Cluster, Panel	Program Manager	Panel development, management, collab cluster			
Networking & Ecosystems Building	IKC3/BIO/BIC/BIOBEC / IBF	IKC3/BIO/BIC/BIOBEC / IBF	Program Manager	Events, online and in person ecosystem development			
Project Library / Tech & IP Portal	IKC3/BIO/BIC/BIOBEC / IBF	IKC3/BIO/BIC/BIOBEC / IBF	Community Manager	Content development and dissemination			
Bioeconomy Talent Hub Jobs & Skills	IKC3/BIO/BIC/BIOBEC / IBF	IKC3/BIO/BIC/BIOBEC / IBF	Community Manager	Skills needs assessment, industry engagement & engagement with Universities on program development			
Bioeconomy Apprenticeships	BIOBEC / IBF / MTU	BIOBEC / IBF / MTU	Program Manager	Development of apprenticeships with University, suggested 10 week program, 4 intakes per year			
Dissemination & Communication	IKC3/BIO/BIC/BIOBEC / IBF	BIOBEC	Community Manager	Website Development, Social Media Channels, Press, Blogs, Newsletter			
		Annual Core Staff costs (€)		Annual Costs Operational (€)			
BBEC Offering		Program Manager	Community Manager	Consumables	Travel	Consultants	Academic
Accredited programs level 6 – 9 signposting	12025,00						
Schools Engagement Program		13876,78		250,00	1500,00		
Knowledge Exchange (Microcredentials)	12025,00			5000,00	1500,00		
Bioeconomy Accelerator / Enterprise Dev	12025,00			250,00			
Mentorship & Advisory	12025,00			250,00		10800,00	
Networking & Ecosystems Building	12025,00			250,00	1000,00		
Project Library / Tech & IP Portal		13876,79			1000,00		
Bioeconomy Talent Hub Jobs & Skills		13876,79		5000,00			
Bioeconomy Apprenticeships	12025,00						
Dissemination & Communication		13876,79		2000,00			
		Expenditure Breakdown				Non-Center Costs	
Team		Salary (€)	PPRSI @ 11% (€)	Total Cost Yr (€)		Planning of Academic Programs	
Program / Center Manager	65000,00		7150,00	72150,00		Development of Academic programs	
Community Manager – Events, PR, Comms etc	50000,00		5507,15	55507,15		Access to facilities / offices – hosted by Universities	
		Annual Staff costs (€)		127657,15			
Other costs		Description					
Mentors	3 sessions/day @ 1800/day	36 sessions per year (12 days)	10800,00				
Event hosting	Room Hire & Catering		5000,00				
Travel	National events		5000,00				
Online Collab Tools	Canvas, Miro, Zoom	annual renewal	1000,00				
Abadoo Hosting	Careers & Skills mining	annual renewal	5000,00				
Website Support & Hosting	Development & Hosting	annual renewal	2000,00				
		Annual running cost (€)		28800,00			
Total annual operational Costs (€)				156457,15			
Total Lifetime operational Costs (€)		(3 years)		469371,45			
Website development 115000		once off expenditure Yr1 Mth1		15000,00			
Total Lifetime Costs (€)				484371,45			

Financial sustainability assessment

As discussed, the Irish BBEC will require grant funding. The funding requirement is based on a 3 year operational cycle. Challenges to the viability of the Irish BBEC have been assessed and will be discussed in more detail as part of the overall business plan.

This project has received funding from the Bio-based Industries Joint Undertaking (JU) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101023381. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the Bio-based Industries Consortium.

Mediterranean BBEC

Necessary investments

The Mediterranean BBEC promotes the development of a circular bioeconomy in the Mediterranean area by facilitating the delivery of better bioeconomy education and training services related to the bioeconomy. The Center's vision is to become the reference point for bioeconomy education and training for both EU and Extra-EU countries, with a specific focus on Mediterranean bioeconomy conditions.

The Centre does not start from the development of an existing entity/institution, so it needs to be funded as a new legal entity. This involves starting time and costs, including legal costs for the establishment of the Centre. It is expected that the Centre will not have a physical location but will be hosted at the premises of one of the partner institutions. The activities will be largely held on line, through web facilities.

Hence, the necessary investments will include two main streams:

- Investment for Consortium establishment;
- Investment for Centre establishment.

These two cost streams are further analyzed in the Capex section.

- Legal and administrative costs for establish the Consortium;
- Website/online platform;
- IT hardware & software;
- Personnel for starting activities;

Capital expenditures needed for starting (Capex)

The capital expenditures needed for starting are estimated around 90k euro, may be in range of 110k. This amount may have some flexibility due to lack of use of buildings etc., but will need a high quality web facility to make sure the Centre is effective and has a good starting. However, the main items are described below.

Investment for Consortium's establishment

Legal and administrative costs for establish the Consortium

The first investments are related to transaction costs for establishing the Consortium. However, legal and administrative costs change country by country and will depend on the legal form taken. This is expected to be a non-for profit consortium among member entities. At the moment this is not established yet, so the estimate is a rough figure for Italy. Items considered include: Administrative labour for coordination and brokerage; Legal consultancy; Notary fees.

Others

Considering the interregional dimension of the Centre, the only other item considered was travel, accommodation & reimbursements costs.

Investment for Centre's establishment

Personnel for starting activities

Personnel will be needed for starting up the Centre, including design and activation of the online platform. The items considered were: Management labour; Administrative labour; and

Communication service. For each of these items was defined an effort of 1 person-month (1.5 for administrative labour).

Website/Online platform

One of the peculiarities of the Centre is to be totally virtual. Hence, a website online platform will be designed as a starting activity, even before the official launch of the Centre. Indeed, the business idea foresees that the Centre will promote online several services, such as: education and training opportunities; educational material; internships and mentoring opportunities; events for bioeconomy; news. In this vein, it is important to underline that the estimated costs for setting up this platform (30k€) refer to a service that expects the platform as a collector of various materials and facilitator of training proposals outside the Centre, rather than Open and Distance Learning (ODL) platform. In fact, the complexity of an ODL platform would require a much greater initial investment.

IT hardware & software

General and specific costs have been considered. The former are fixed costs, such as IT software licenses, IT Infrastructure, Phone line and Internet connection, and Lighting/Energy.

Instead, due to specific needs for education and training, or communication or administrative purposes it might arise a request for specific hardware or software. All these items were considered. However, depending on the specific organization this might be covered by subscriptions by member institutions.

Legal consultancy

A legal consultancy to guarantee the application of the Regulation (EU) 2016/ 679 (GDPR) was considered due to the complexity of the topic.

Others

Also in this case, travel, accommodation and reimbursements were taken into account with a specific budget.

Detailed investment plan

We designed a rough investment plan during the first year of activities (see excel file). However, this can be made more detailed as we progress with the specification of activities.

Operational expenses – OPEX

Operational budget (depending on the # and type of courses)

The costs for each activity are reported in Annex 1.

A summary of the operational budget is given in the table below for a standard year (3-5).

Item	Cost (€)
Management, administration and general costs	119,000
Training the trainers	14,500
Online services	21,000
Dissemination & communication	20,500
Internships enabler	6,900
Mentoring by industry	10,900
Identification of priorities, skill profiles, education and training needs	6,300
Web facility	2,000
Total	201,100

Most of the costs are related to personnel. The amount connected to teaching activity is not very high, as the Centre is expected to provide only a limited number of courses, mostly in the area of “training the trainer” activities. We assumed the capacity to cover two countries (Italy and Spain) with

one event each. In the longer term, the actual cost will depend on the level of activation of courses and other activities, that can be only guessed at the time of writing this report.

Teachers, trainers and external experts

The integration of structured teachers or trainers into the staff is not envisaged, initially. Hence, teachers, trainers and external experts will be all paid on the level of activity (teaching hours). An estimate within each activity has been made. However, it is important to underline that coherently with the activities, a variety of professionals will be involved: Teachers and trainers (bioeconomy experts & education experts), Education experts (per country) to validate material and proposals; Tutors internal for internships and mentoring; Tutors from industry for internships; Mentors from industry; Industry representatives for job days.

Buildings

There are no expenses for buildings or offices. If a cost is envisaged by the institution hosting the staff, the cost for renting an office would be the maximum expected. Costs for location for teaching in person will be faced case by case and are included in the costs of courses. This is also related to the choice of keep flexibility about location and to exploit in kind hosting by partner institutions.

Management and Admin

Management and administration costs represent the highest cost, accounting for more than 50% of the OPEX. They will mostly consist of salaries (director and secretary), legal costs and fees. About this item there was a discussion during one of the specific IRWG meeting. In particular, the main point was the number of hired workers. Indeed, currently, only two figures a director and a secretary have been considered as employed by the Centre with all the other tasks will be complemented by in kind staff contribution by member institutions (e.g. from universities and clusters). The observed criticism was that, in this way, it is missed an education expert that coordinates and guarantees the consistency of the educational and training offer. Indeed, such figure should also work full-time for the Centre. This observation brought to decide that the director is expected to be, at least in the first years, a person involved in education with competencies in management. Moreover, this person will take care of the relationships between partners within the Centre and with external stakeholders. After five years (once that the Centre is well-established), the figure of the director can be split in two: a General Manager – more focused on strategies, business plans, relationships and corporate image – and an Education Manager – more focused on the educational part, coordinating trainers, materials, and tools.

Marketing/website

Most of the costs under this chapter would be again salaries paid to own staff. In addition the following costs may require external services:

- Costs for hosting and update of the website
- Costs for communication/Conference materials
- Costs for participation/organization to information days/Job days
- Cost for external services to run a Newsletter
- Costs linked to social media marketing

Others

Some other costs may be envisaged that would be mainly connected to management and administration but may have also other aims. These would include:

- Travel costs for different kinds of activities and general needs of updates and networking;
- IT maintenance;
- Costs for accountancy;
- Costs for translation consultancy;
- Costs for renting buildings for info days or for job days;

Revenues

Public funding

Several sources of public funding are expected, in particular for project-based activities.

European funds

- ESF
- RDPs?
- Others...?

International funds

- PRIMA
- BLUEMED
- Others...?

National/local funds

- Italian Recovery fund (PNRR)
- Italian Interprofessional funds
- Regional funds for Education and Training

Almost 40% of total revenues were considered from public funds. In absolute values, it was taken into account a revenue of 65k €.

Participants payments

The basis for the working of the Centre will be an annual fee to be paid by members. This will cover the basic staff costs and general costs of running the Centre. A group of 15 members was considered, taking into account an annual fee per member of 2k € (less than 170 €/month). This fee was discussed with the IRWG. The general opinion is that this fee is not too high for companies and other entities but it really important to justify this expense with a image or economic return, and this will be necessary especially after the start-up phase.

For some activities, payments of fees by participants is expected. In particular, reasonable scaling of participants was considered, starting with 20 participants the first year, 30 participants the second year and 50 participants from third to fifth year. A standard fee of 500€ per participant was chosen. Also on this point there was a discussion with the IRWG. The final suggestion was to consider a more reasonable scenario in which the number of participants is higher (ex. 250 participants per year), with a lower fee (ex. 100 €). With this numbers the final result is the same (25k € per year from participants fees). Nevertheless, the standard fee of 500 €/participant was referred as possible only if the final certification provided by the courses justifies it. This is the reason why it was decided to leave the highest fee within the Excel table, i.e. for stimulating the discussion on certifications and professional qualification that the Centre will provide.

In-kind contribution is also expected by industries participation in coaching and mentoring and by member institutions, with a lump sum value of around 75k € per year.

Cash flow – in the short and long term

The annual cash flow is presented in the attached file.

Financial sustainability assessment

Financial sustainability will be key in the initial year to allow investment. For this reason the current rationale is to ask members to provide a fee sufficient to cover fixed costs (or to provide in-kind substitutes). Additional activities will be paid based on ad hoc revenues connected to the services provided or on a project basis.

 Bio-based Industries
Consortium

 Horizon 2020
European Union Funding
for Research & Innovation

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Annexes to Mediterranean BBEC financial plan

Annex 1

MEDITERRANEAN BBEC	Description	Objective	People involved – PMs; Other costs	A Units * units costs (€) = total	B Operational budget (sum of A values)	C Income
Management, administration and general costs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The activity, based on the governance structure, covers one director and one secretary full time. - General costs for running the Centre include accountancy service and translation consultancy; 	To guarantee the ordinary and extra-ordinary management of the centre.	<u>Internal:</u> Director – 12 PM Secretary – 12 PM <u>External:</u> Accountant – 2 PM Translator – 2 PM	12*6,000=72,000 12*3,000=36,000 2*3,000=6,000 2*2,500=5,000	119,000	
Training the trainers – at different Educational levels;	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training pathways for teachers and trainers (online & in person): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o For various educational levels (school, academia, VET, lifelong learning); o At various levels following students' background (e.g. basic, intermediate, advanced) - (Possible) tutorial/webinars made by education & training experts and/or communication experts. 	The two main learning objectives for learners will be: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> increasing knowledge, competencies and skills in teaching bioeconomy; and raising awareness in existing methodologies, approaches and tools in teaching to different levels of education. The course will be tailored on the learners' background (e.g. specific courses for school teachers or for lifelong learning trainers)	<u>Internal:</u> Teachers and trainers (bioeconomy experts & education experts) – 3 PM Communication and dissemination experts – 0.3 PM <u>External:</u> IT experts – 0.1 PM Educational tools	3*3000=9000 0.3*3,000=900 0.1*6,000=600 4,000	14,500	
Online services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Matching demand and supply of Education and Training service by brokerage and matchmaking activities; - Valorisation of existing teaching material first and then creating common teaching materials: Collection & selection of teaching material (copyright 	Valorisation of existing teaching material first and then creating common teaching materials;	<u>Internal:</u> Education experts – 3 PM <u>External:</u> IT experts/computer consultant 2 PM	3*3,000=9,000 2*6,000=12,000	21,000	

	check); Updating old material and creation of new one;					
Dissemination & communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Online service (platform): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Newsletter (periodically) for events and opportunities; o Reminders for inactive users; - Periodical events (e.g. annually): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Info days; o Job days. 	Increasing public awareness about bioeconomy and bioeconomy education and training.	<u>Internal:</u> Education experts (per country) to validate material and proposals– 1 PM Newsletter managers – 1 PM Staff to organize periodical events – 2 PM <u>Materials and gadgets</u> <u>Software for newsletter</u> <u>Building rent for info/job days</u>	1*3,000=3,000 1*3,000=3,000 2*3,000=6,000 5,000 500 3,000	20,500	
Internships enabler	Tutoring for subscribed students (<u>fee for service</u>). Brokerage between firms and those who apply for the internship. The intern will be followed by a tutor that will evaluate her/his progresses and her/his satisfaction. Also the company's opinion will be taken into account.	Matching human resources and industries enabling the internships. The scope of the activity is to provide training through the practical learning. Furthermore, the ambition is to establish a win-win approach, providing the right human resource to the company and, on the other hand, provide a job opportunity to the human resource.	<u>Internal:</u> Administrative labour to coordinate internships (bureaucratical issues) – 0.8 PM Tutors – 0.5 PM <u>External:</u> Tutors from industry for internships – 0.5 PM	0.8*3,000=2,400 0.5*3,000=1,500 0.5*6,000=3,000	6,900	
Mentoring by industry	Mentoring for subscribed students (<u>fee for service</u>). Brokerage between firms and those who apply for the mentoring service. The Centre will take care of all the	Similarly to the internship, the scope of the activity is to provide training through the practical learning and taking advantage from the experience of professionals.	<u>Internal:</u> Administrative labour to coordinate mentoring (bureaucratical issues) – 0.8 PM Tutors – 0.5 PM	0.8*3,000=2,400	10,900	

	bureaucratic and administrative steps to finalize the activity. The students will be tutored by an expert that will follow their progresses and their satisfaction. Also the company's opinion will be took into account.		<u>External:</u> Industry representatives for mentoring – 1 PM	0.5*5,000=2,500 1*6,000=6,000		
Identification of priorities, skill profiles, education and training needs;	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identification of <i>personas</i> and coherent pathways (together with industry); - Continuous update of needs, priorities and, consequently, of <i>personas</i>; - Periodical events (e.g. annually or half yearly): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Workshops or conferences with all the relevant actors; - Periodical surveys to involved firms. 	Maintaining up to date the Centre in terms of job trends, industrial and private sector needs, education and training for public administration, possibilities for marginalized people (e.g. NEETs).	<u>Internal:</u> Human Resources expert – 1 PM Staff to update – 0.2 PM Administrative Labour – 0.1 PM <u>External:</u> Industry Human Resources experts – 0.3 PM Industry representatives – 0.1 PM	1*3,000=3,000 0.2*3,000=600 0.1*3,000=300 0.3*6,000=1,800 0.1*6,000=600	6,300	
Web facility	- Platform maintenance	Ordinary maintenance of the platform for its correct functioning.	<u>External:</u> IT technicians – 1 PM	1*2,000 = 2,000	2,000	

Danish/Central Denmark Region BBEC

Necessary investments

The specific Danish BBEC is probably going to be established in existing facilities at Agro Business Park where the board has expressed interest in housing this. Already now, a UN SDG 17 Business Center is at the premises, and this could be an inspiration to develop the BBEC with a more specialized focus.

Developing the BBEC from a feasibility study in the EU-funded project towards a fully functional BBEC requires some 'patient capital'/Philanthropy/ investments.

The investments will mainly be in human capital a CEI/project leader and communication skills, since the BBEC educational activities will be held at existing facilities at partner sites.

The investment will be needed for the establishment of web portal, for finding courses.

Capital expenditures needed for starting (Capex)

The BioBec does not start from scratch and all the supporting institutions have their own budget and own business models that the Biobec can only influence marginally. We hope that with an investment in the startup project, we can develop a business plan that can increase the 'size of the cake' instead of competing.

Concept development, marketing, sales, contact with customers and institutions, and ministries will require significant human resources. The right creative and structured person with contact in business and the educational system is needed.

Detailed investment plan

During the project, we developed the first rough plan for the necessary investments (an investment roadmap), including a detailed plan (as possible) for the expected revenue stream, cash flow etc.

This in turn requires a suggestion for a realistic course plan – the curriculum – the basics of the BBEC and still, there has to be a lot of potential space for developing other/new courses, meeting the needs of the regional businesses. Indeed, we also need a plan for the identification of potential collaborations and synergies with further relevant stakeholders for the developed BBECs.

Operational expenses – OPEX

OPEX should be calculated for each individual course as they will vary considerably in content, length, degree of specialization, need for excursions etc., and then summed up into a bank of courses, where you calculate the cash flow for each course, and thereby the liquidity budget/ cash flow of the BBEC (see below).

Add to this, the expenses of the management, administration, and communication, partly financed by the initial investment, and partly financed by course overhead.

Teachers

A proportion of teachers used for the courses can be used (can contribute to the teaching as part of dissemination obligations of their present job, but for courses and longer semester teaching, the teachers will have to be paid by the BBEC.

A typical norm would be for innovative courses that there should be 2 hours of preparation/planning for one hour of confronting. For instance, a course on 20 hours of confronting would require 60 hours of payment.

The teacher would need salary plus e.g. (to be negotiated) 60% overhead. Let us say 50 € as raw salary would result in 4.800 € in resulting salary in the mentioned 20 hours confronting course.

Add to this the rentals of facilities, overhead to the administration, and management of another 60%

Buildings

We expect that the facilities can be rented at existing institutions (Agro Business Park, Aarhus University, Asmildkloster etc.)

Management and Admin

The task to develop the BBEC concept and the individual courses is an ongoing challenge. We believe that we need to have 3 years of salary for 1,5 employees – a total of 500.000 €

The concept development and management of the BBEC require that the CEO should not spend time in the first years on fundraising. Rather, the time should be spent on communication, networking and further developing the reality-adapted business model for the second BBEC phase in years 3-6. That second phase is when the sustainability of the BBEC will be tested.

In addition, there are administrative and communicative expenses continuously.

Marketing/website

Developing a new BBEC institutional brand require investments in human resources and communication. The concept, the customers, the customer relationships, the channels, etc. have to be built from scratch. A BBEC does not exist without a website, Linked In profile etc., and yet the management must have some content already by day one.

In addition to that, traditional 'cold canvas' marketing is relevant to attract investors, customers, partners, and resources.

Revenues

Public funding

In the specific case of Central Denmark Region BBEC, we believe that we have already identified 2-4 *potential* investors. It should be stressed, that this has not been confirmed, but are possibilities based on the business model workshop to illustrate the opportunities for this case.

Participants payments

Concerning the payments by the participants/students, we have to develop a model where the value of the courses for individuals/students/business employees will match the payment.

'Students' (not in job) should be paid by national public taxpayer payments (and the course value accredited with corresponding ECTS points), whereas business employees or public servants in jobs potentially are paid by 'life-long learning obligations' by the companies and institutions.

To a certain extent, the 'customers'/students can share their experiences and use their personal experiences to enrich the other students.

Potentially, we could also give courses specifically designed for a large company, e.g. Arla, Hedeselskabet or large farmers' cooperatives to create additional revenue.

Cash flow – in the short and long term

Cash flow diagrams are available but will be elaborated further to reach a sustainable balance.

Cash Flow/Liquidity budget, monthly													
	m1	m2	m3	m4	m5	m6	m7	m8	m9	m10	m11	m12	Total Year 1
CAPEX													
Concept development			4000	4000	4000	4000	4000	4000	4000	4000	4000	4000	44000
website				15000				10000					25000
admin			2000	2000	5000	5000	2000		3000	1000			20000
Opex													
salaries													
Coordinator and maketing	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	120000
Teachers			8000	8000	8000	8000	4000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	76000
Travel expences		1000	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000	10000
rentals for office	600	600	600	600	600	600	600	600	600	600	600	600	7200
rental for auditorium			1200	1200	1200	1200		1200	1200	1200	1200	1200	10800
Bbec and course marketing	1350	1350	1350	1350	1350	1350	1350	1350	1350	1350	1350	1350	16200
Website						2500				2500			5000
total costs													334200
Revenue													
public support (Municipality, region, state)													
Municipality	7500	7500	7500	7500	7500	7500	7500	7500	7500	7500	7500	7500	90000
region			21000							21000			42000
state													0
EU													0
Membership fee	25000						25000						50000
participants fee					10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	1000	71000
total revenue													253000
Balance													-81200

Cash Flow/Liquidity budget, monthly													
	m1	m2	m3	m4	m5	m6	m7	m8	m9	m10	m11	m12	Total Year 2
CAPEX													
Concept development				3000				3000					6000
website													0
admin													0
Opex													
salaries													
Coordinator and maketing	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	120000
Teachers	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	4000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	92000
Travel expences	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000	11000
rentals for office	600	600	600	600	600	600	600	600	600	600	600	600	7200
rental for facilities			1200	1200	1200	1200		1200	1200	1200	1200	1200	10800
Bbec and course marketing	1350	1350	1350	1350	1350	1350	1350	1350	1350	1350	1350	1350	16200
Website						2500				2500			5000
total costs													268200
Revenue													
public support (Municipality, region, state)													
Municipality	7500	7500	7500	7500	7500	7500	7500	7500	7500	7500	7500	7500	90000
region			21000							21000			42000
state													0
EU													0
Membership fee	25000						25000						50000
participants fee	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	120000
total revenue													302000
Balance													33800

Financial sustainability assessment

This initial work has clarified that the Danish BBEC must find additional revenue sources and/or reduce costs to reach a balance. The work during coming months will deal with this balance and develop new sources of income with the participating partners.

Annex 3 Funding opportunities for BBECs

European funding ecosystem

Below, a general analysis of the European ecosystem will be entitled to let interested bodies be aware about the investment focus and the match with BIOBEC Project outcomes.

Public funding programmes

Funding programme	Investment focus	Additional information	BIOBEC's link	Link
Horizon Europe - Cluster 6	Research and innovation projects in the field of bioeconomy	This cluster aims at reducing environmental degradation, halting and reversing the decline of biodiversity on land, inland waters and sea and better managing natural resources through transformative changes of the economy and society in both urban and rural areas.	Developing new bio-based products and services, as well as the establishment of new bio-based value chains.	HE – Cluster 6
Erasmus+	Innovation in education and training	Alliances for Innovation aim to strengthen Europe's innovation capacity by boosting innovation through cooperation and flow of knowledge among higher education, vocational education, and training (both initial and continuous), and the broader socio-economic environment, including research.	Developing new educational approaches and organizational solutions to provide education and training services in the bio-based industry.	Erasm us+
Erasmus+ Cooperation for Innovation and the Exchange of Good Practices	Innovation in education and training	This activity provides funding for partnerships between organizations from different countries to work together on projects that promote innovation and the exchange of good practices.	Creating new educational centres in Europe that focus on bioeconomy	Erasm us+
Erasmus+ Support for Policy Reform	Innovation in education and training	This activity provides funding for policy development and implementation in the fields of education, training, and youth.	Creating new educational centres in Europe that focus on bioeconomy, as you could work on developing and implementing policies related to the bioeconomy in the field of education and training.	Erasm us+
Erasmus+ Jean Monnet Activities	Innovation in education and training	This activity provides funding for projects and activities related to the European Union and its integration in the field of higher education. The Jean Monnet actions offer opportunities in the field of higher education and in other fields of education and training.	Creating new educational centres in Europe that focus on bioeconomy, as you could work on projects related to the bioeconomy and its integration into higher education in the EU.	Erasm us+
European Social Fund	Improving employment, social inclusion, and education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Support for education and training of disadvantaged groups, such as low-skilled workers, long-term unemployed or people with disabilities - Support for the development of new education and training programs and initiatives that target the bioeconomy. 	Training and retraining of workers to acquire new skills and knowledge related to the bioeconomy	ESF

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Support for the implementation of policies and strategies that promote the development of the bioeconomy and the creation of new jobs in the sector 		
European Regional Development Fund (ERDF)	Investments that help to boost economic growth, create jobs, and support regional development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Development of new research and innovation centres focused on the bioeconomy - Modernization of existing facilities and infrastructure to create new bio-based education centres - Development of new education and training programs and initiatives that target the bioeconomy - Implementation of policies and strategies that promote the development of the bioeconomy and the creation of new jobs in the sector - Development of new digital technologies and tools to support bio-based education centres 	Developing new business and educational opportunities in the bio-based industry that support regional development and job creation.	<u>ERDF</u>
Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking (CBE-JU)	Research and innovation projects that aim to develop a sustainable bio-based economy in Europe	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Developing new bio-based educational programs and initiatives. -Promoting Entrepreneurship in Bio-based Education. -Supporting the development of new digital technologies and tools to support bio-based education -Providing training and professional development opportunities for bio-based education. 	Funding bio-based curriculum, educational materials, and bio-based technologies. Support new business models and strategies for BBECs. e-Learning platforms or other digital tools. Development of training programs or workshops.	<u>CBE-JU</u>
LIFE	Environmental and climate action projects	LIFE is the European Union's funding programme for the environment and climate action. The programme provides funding for projects that contribute to the development and implementation of EU environmental and climate policy.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Construction and renovation of bio-based educational centres- -Implementation of bio-based educational programs and initiatives. -Funding for the development of bio-based educational programs and initiatives that focus on sustainable resource use, circular economy principles, and the development of bio-based products and services 	<u>LIFE</u>

Mediterranean BBEC

Below, each BBEC have provided feedback about an extended list of regional/local instruments, and these have been further analysed.

Name	EIC Accelerator
Short description	The EIC Accelerator supports high-risk, high-potential small and medium-sized enterprises and innovators to help them develop and bring new products, services and business models that could drive economic growth onto the market. Project Budget: € 0.5 and € 2.5 million. investments (direct equity investments) of up to €15 million
Duration	Multi-year program
Application Deadlines	Specific application deadlines may be determined for individual projects
Financial support type	Grant-only, blended finance, equity based
Geographical coverage	Europe
Sectorial coverage	Various sectors, including but not limited to infrastructure, digitalization, sustainable development, education, research, and innovation.
Type of Applicants	Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMES)
Link	https://eic.ec.europa.eu/eic-funding-opportunities/eic-accelerator_en

Name	Eurostars
Short description	Eurostars is a funding instrument that supports innovative SMEs and project partners (large companies, universities, research organisations and other types of organisations) by funding international collaborative R&D and innovation projects. By participating, organisations from 37 countries can access public funding for international collaborative R&D projects in all fields.
Duration	12-36 months
Application Deadlines	Specific application deadlines may be determined for individual projects
Financial support type	Up to 300.000€ per beneficiary but depending on national bodies from Eureka
Geographical coverage	Europe
Sectorial coverage	Various sectors, including but not limited to infrastructure, digitalization, sustainable development, education, research, and innovation.
Type of Applicants	Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMES)
Link	https://www.eurekanetwork.org/open-calls/

Name	INNOWIDE
Short description	The INNOWIDE pilot call intends to bring European highly innovative SMEs to the forefront of international markets by opening two calls that will allow them to conduct Viability Assessment Projects (VAPs) in cooperation with local stakeholders. SMEs can develop product- (process- or service-) market combinations and partnerships with strategic counterparts to generate business opportunities and compete in new and emerging markets.
Duration	Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMES)
Application Deadlines	Open call with cut off dates
Financial support type	Maximum €60 000 lump sum per project
Geographical coverage	Europe
Sectorial coverage	Various sectors, including but not limited to infrastructure, digitalization, sustainable development, education, research, and innovation.
Type of Applicants	Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMES)
Link	https://www.eurekanetwork.org/programmes/innowwide/

Name	INNOWIDE
Short description	The INNOWIDE pilot call intends to bring European highly innovative SMEs to the forefront of international markets by opening two calls that will allow them to conduct Viability Assessment Projects (VAPs) in cooperation with local stakeholders. SMEs can develop product- (process- or service-) market combinations and partnerships with strategic counterparts to generate business opportunities and compete in new and emerging markets.
Duration	Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMES)
Application Deadlines	Open call with cut off dates
Financial support type	Maximum €60 000 lump sum per project
Geographical coverage	Europe
Sectorial coverage	Various sectors, including but not limited to infrastructure, digitalization, sustainable development, education, research, and innovation.
Type of Applicants	Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMES)
Link	https://www.eurekanetwork.org/programmes/innowwide/

Name	Financial Support for Third Parties (FSTP)
Short description	Cascade funding , also known as Financial Support for Third Parties (FSTP), is a Commission mechanism to distribute public funding to assist beneficiaries, such as start-ups, scale-ups, SMEs and/or mid-caps, in the uptake or development of digital innovation. Cascade funding is a European Commission mechanism that distributes smaller amounts of public funds in a more agile way, supporting specific topics such as the incorporation of new technologies, the promotion of start-ups and sector pioneers, etc. The main objective of this funding method is to simplify administrative procedures for applicant entities, mostly SMEs and start-ups, thus allowing some EU-funded projects to issue, in turn, open calls for further funding. In other words, cascade funding is a simplified public funding opportunity, designed to facilitate a greater capillarity of EC funds and actions, facilitating the participation of SMEs and start-ups, since for them, participating in a European project means dealing with a large amount of bureaucracy.
Duration	Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMES)
Application Deadlines	Open call with cut off dates
Financial support type	€50.000 to €150.000
Geographical coverage	Europe
Sectorial coverage	Various sectors, including but not limited to infrastructure, digitalization, sustainable development, education, research, and innovation.
Type of Applicants	Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMES) and start-ups
Link	https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/competitive-calls

Name	Eurocluster cascade funding
Short description	Euroclusters are cross-sectoral, interdisciplinary and trans-European strategic initiatives gathering industry clusters and other economic actors, such as research organisations, companies, etc. to implement the EU Industrial Strategy. They will create new business opportunities for SMEs and integrate them better in European and global strategic value chains. The Euroclusters build upon European Commission's experience with the 4 strands of "European Cluster Partnerships", supported under Horizon 2020 (Innovation) and COSME (Internationalisation, Excellence and Smart Specialisation Investments).
Duration	Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMES)
Application Deadlines	Open call with cut off dates
Financial support type	€50.000 to €150.000
Geographical coverage	Europe

Sectorial coverage	Industry clusters and other economic actors, such as research organisations, companies, etc. to implement the EU Industrial Strategy.
Type of Applicants	Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMES) and start-ups
Link	https://eisma.ec.europa.eu/news/euroclusters-are-launching-their-first-cascade-funding-calls-2023-03-29_en

Name	The National Recovery and Resilience Plan
Short description	Outlines the objectives, reforms and investments that Italy intends to carry out through NextGenerationEU funds to mitigate the COVID-19 socio-economic impact and make Italy a fairer, greener and more inclusive country, with a more competitive, dynamic and innovative economy.
Duration	Multi-year program
Application Deadlines	Specific application deadlines may be determined for individual projects
Financial support type	Various types: grants, loans, and investments
Geographical coverage	Italy
Sectorial coverage	Various sectors, including but not limited to infrastructure, digitalization, sustainable development, education, research, and innovation.
Type of Applicants	Different types of entities, including government institutions, businesses, research organizations, educational institutions, and other relevant stakeholders.
Link	https://www.agenziacoesione.gov.it/comunicazione/piano-nazionale-di-ripresa-e-resilienza/?lang=en

Name	ENISA
Short description	ENISA is the Spanish National Innovation Company that provides financial support to innovative Spanish companies.
Duration	Ongoing program
Application Deadlines	Calls for funding
Financial support type	Equity, investment and loans
Geographical coverage	Spain
Sectorial coverage	Technology, innovation, and entrepreneurship
Type of Applicants	Eligible applicants include innovative startups and SMEs (small and medium-sized enterprises) based in Spain.
Link	https://www.enisa.es/

Name	Fundación Biodiversidad
Short description	Fundación Biodiversidad is a Spanish foundation that promotes biodiversity conservation, sustainable development, and environmental projects..
Duration	Ongoing program
Application Deadlines	Specific application deadlines for its various programs and initiatives.
Financial support type	Grants, subsidies, and other grants
Geographical coverage	Spain
Sectorial coverage	Related to biodiversity conservation, sustainable development, climate change adaptation, ecosystem restoration, and other environmental topics.
Type of Applicants	Eligible applicants may include NGOs, research institutions, public administrations, private enterprises, and other entities working in the field of environmental conservation and sustainability.
Link	https://fundacion-biodiversidad.es/

Name	Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica y el Reto Demográfico (MITECO)
Short description	MITECO is the Spanish ministry responsible for environmental policies, ecological transition, and addressing demographic challenges.
Duration	Ongoing program
Application Deadlines	Specific application deadlines for its various programs and initiatives.
Financial support type	Grants, subsidies
Geographical coverage	Spain
Sectorial coverage	Sectors related to environmental protection, ecological transition, renewable energy, climate change mitigation, biodiversity conservation, water management, and more.
Type of Applicants	Eligible applicants may include public administrations, research institutions, NGOs, private enterprises, and other entities working in the field of environmental protection and ecological transition.
Link	https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/

Name	Regional funds for Education and Training (IT)
Short description	Provides financial support for adult learners.
Duration	Not specified
Application Deadlines	Not specified
Financial support type	Fees paid by learners, financial support for adult learners, private education
Geographical coverage	Italy
Sectorial coverage	Not specified
Type of Applicants	Adult learners
Link	https://eurydice.eacea.ec.europa.eu/national-education-systems/italy/adult-education-and-training-funding

Name	CEDEFOP
Short description	CEDEFOP is an agency of the European Union that provides expertise and support in vocational education and training (VET). It aims to contribute to the development and improvement of VET systems across Europe.
Duration	Ongoing program
Application Deadlines	Not specified
Financial support type	Expertise, research, and knowledge-sharing support in the field of vocational education and training. It may offer funding opportunities for specific projects or research initiatives through grants
Geographical coverage	EU-members states
Sectorial coverage	CEDEFOP focuses on vocational education and training across various sectors and industries, aiming to improve the quality, relevance, and effectiveness of VET systems and policies.
Type of Applicants	Policymakers, researchers, education and training providers, and other stakeholders involved in vocational education and training at the European level.
Link	https://www.cedefop.europa.eu/es

Name	European Social Fund (ESF)
Short description	European Union's structural funds aimed at promoting employment, social inclusion, and investment in human capital. It supports various initiatives and projects across member states to enhance employability, education, and social cohesion.
Duration	multi-year programming periods
Application Deadlines	Specific programs, projects, and member states.
Financial support type	Grants, subsidies, and other funding mechanisms
Geographical coverage	SI European Union member states across different regions and territories.
Sectorial coverage	Employment, vocational training, education, social inclusion, entrepreneurship, and equal opportunities.
Type of Applicants	Public authorities, non-profit organizations, educational institutions, employers, social partners, and other entities involved in initiatives related to employment, skills, and social inclusion.
Link	https://ec.europa.eu/european-social-fund-plus/en

Name	Rural Development Programs under the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)
Short description	Support the sustainable development of rural areas and agricultural communities across European Union member states.
Duration	Rural Development Programs are part of the CAP, which operates in multi-year programming periods. The current programming period is 2021-2027.
Application Deadlines	Specific programs, projects, and member states.
Financial support type	Grants, subsidies, and other funding mechanisms
Geographical coverage	SI European Union member states including their rural areas and agricultural communities.
Sectorial coverage	Agriculture, forestry, rural tourism, environmental conservation, rural infrastructure, farm diversification, and socio-economic development of rural communities.
Type of Applicants	Eligible applicants for Rural Development Program funding may include farmers, agricultural enterprises, rural businesses, local authorities, non-profit organizations, and other entities involved in rural development initiatives.
Link	https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/common-agricultural-policy/rural-development/country_en

Name	PRIMA (Partnership for Research and Innovation in the Mediterranean Area)
Short description	Develop research and innovation capacities in the Mediterranean region to address water and food challenges. It focuses on promoting sustainable agriculture, water management, and agro-food value chains
Duration	Multi-year duration with specific calls for proposals issued periodically.
Application Deadlines	Depending on the specific funding opportunities and project themes.
Financial support type	Competitive calls for proposals.
Geographical coverage	Mediterranean region, which includes countries from Europe, North Africa, and the Middle East.
Sectorial coverage	Agriculture, water management, and agro-food value chains.
Type of Applicants	Research institutions, universities, industry partners, NGOs
Link	https://prima-med.org/

Name	BlueMed Initiative Funding Opportunities
Short description	Support sustainable blue growth and marine research and innovation in the Mediterranean region. It offers funding opportunities to support research, innovation, and capacity-building activities in these areas.
Duration	Multi-year duration with specific calls for proposals issued periodically.
Application Deadlines	Depending on the specific funding opportunities and project themes.
Financial support type	Research, innovation, and capacity-building activities related to the marine and maritime sectors, through competitive calls for proposals.
Geographical coverage	Mediterranean region, which includes countries from Europe, North Africa, and the Middle East.
Sectorial coverage	Marine biodiversity, coastal management, sustainable fisheries, aquaculture, marine renewable energy, marine biotechnology, marine pollution, and blue tourism, among others.
Type of Applicants	Research institutions, universities, industry partners, NGOs
Link	http://www.blumed-initiative.eu/funding-opportunities/

Name	Technology Transfer R&D Projects "Cervera".
Short description	Strengthening the innovation capabilities of SMEs and mid-cap companies, through the contracting of R&D activities to knowledge-generating centres or the execution of R&D projects in collaboration with these entities, in one of the priority technologies "Cervera".
Duration	Multi-year duration with specific calls for proposals issued periodically.
Application Deadlines	Open Application
Financial support type	Partially reimbursable grant. The company must finance at least 10% of the project budget with its own resources.
Geographical coverage	Spain.
Sectorial coverage	Advanced materials, circular economy, energy transition, smart manufacturing, health technologies, safe and healthy food chain, deep learning and artificial intelligence, advanced mobile networks, intelligent transportation
Type of Applicants	SMEs and MIDCAPs
Link	https://www.cdti.es/index.asp?MP=100&MS=881&MN=2

Name	EUROEQUITY
Short description	Euroquity is a business-oriented platform that connects entrepreneurs, start-ups, and businesses with potential investors. It provides a matchmaking service, allowing companies to present their projects and investment opportunities to a network of investors. Euroquity aims to facilitate the funding process by connecting entrepreneurs and investors, fostering collaboration, and supporting the growth of innovative businesses.
Duration	Ongoing
Application Deadlines	NA.
Financial support type	Private Investment
Geographical coverage	European Countries
Sectorial coverage	Various sectors including bioeconomy and education
Type of Applicants	Entrepreneurs, start-ups, and businesses
Link	https://www.euroquity.com/en/home

Name	Foro capital PYMES
Short description	Platform focused on connecting small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) with potential investors and providing funding opportunities. It aims to support the growth and development of SMEs through financial resources, networking, and mentorship.
Duration	Ongoing
Application Deadlines	NA
Financial support type	Private investment, funding opportunities
Geographical coverage	Spain mainly
Sectorial coverage	Various sectors including but not limited to education, bioeconomy, and innovation.
Type of Applicants	SMEs
Link	https://forocapitalpymes.com/

Name	The World Business Angels Investment Forum
Short description	International organization that aims to foster angel investment and support entrepreneurship globally. It provides a platform for angel investors, entrepreneurs, and policymakers to connect, exchange knowledge, and explore investment opportunities.
Duration	Ongoing
Application Deadlines	NA
Financial support type	Private funding. Angel investment, funding opportunities
Geographical coverage	Global coverage
Sectorial coverage	Various sectors including but not limited to education, innovation, and entrepreneurship.
Type of Applicants	Entrepreneurs, startups, angel investors, policymakers, and related stakeholders.
Link	https://wbaforum.org/

Eastern Europe BBEC

Name	HORIZON EUROPE - Expanding Academia-Enterprise Collaborations
Short description	HORIZON-EIE-2024-CONNECT-02-01. Projects results are expected to contribute to 1) improved flows of knowledge, skills, and talents between educational institutions and other innovation ecosystem actors at various levels of development. ills of all involved ecosystem actors to increase innovation potential, inter-sectoral mobility, and market uptake of new technologies 2) improved connections of educational institutions to high-quality remote testing, validation, and up-scaling of innovations delivered by research and technology infrastructures across the EU 3) improved competence of students, graduates, researchers, and workforce to launch, run, and lead successful and profitable start-ups.
Duration	36 months
Application Deadlines	19/09/2024
Financial support type	Public funding. Coordination and Support Action- Lump Sum Grant
Geographical coverage	Collaborative European coverage
Sectorial coverage	Educational and research institutions are considered key places for knowledge production and innovation, and should be well connected within and beyond their respective regional innovation ecosystems.
Type of Applicants	<i>Research and innovation (related actors such as vocational schools, higher education institutions, public authorities in the field of education and employment, innovation agencies,</i>
Link	https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/horizon-eie-2024-connect-02-01

Name	HORIZON EUROPE - Innovating for climate-neutral rural communities by 2050
Short description	HORIZON-CL6-2024-COMMUNITIES-02-1-two-stage. Multi-actor approach by involving relevant stakeholders from an early stage (e.g. rural communities representatives, small-medium enterprises -SMEs, etc., end-users, local authorities, etc.). Proposals should cover various biogeographical regions with a balanced coverage reflecting the various pedo-climatic zones in Europe in a representative way.
Duration	36 months
Application Deadlines	22/02/2024 – 17/09/2024
Financial support type	Public funding. Innovation Action- Lump Sum Grant
Geographical coverage	Collaborative European coverage
Sectorial coverage	Resilient, inclusive, healthy and green rural, coastal and urban communities
Type of Applicants	Public and private players and making rural areas an attractive place for innovators to work and live.
Link	Link

Name	HORIZON EUROPE New sustainable business and production models for farmers and rural communities
Short description	HORIZON-CL6-2024-COMMUNITIES-02-2-two-stage. All proposals should explore social innovation and innovative forms of cooperation. Proposals must implement the 'multi-actor approach' and ensure adequate involvement of relevant actors of the value chain. Moving towards more sustainable business and production systems requires adequate tools and measurement methods to assess and monitor the multi-performance of farms and rural businesses under different conditions.
Duration	36 months
Application Deadlines	22/02/2024 – 17/09/2024
Financial support type	Public funding. Research and Innovation Action Grant Budget-Based
Geographical coverage	Collaborative European coverage

Sectorial coverage	rural communities as well as farmers
Type of Applicants	citizens, private companies and public organisations with farmers to increase demand for sustainable agriculture and create a market for new business, cooperation and production models
Link	Link

Name	HORIZON EUROPE Addressing biodiversity decline and promoting Nature-based Solutions in higher education
Short description	HORIZON-CL6-2023-BIODIV-01-8. This topic aims to contribute to education, skills development and awareness raising about biodiversity loss, and how this can be addressed, notably with Nature-based Solutions (NBS), in the higher education sector. This is fundamental to further implement and upscale NBS and to mainstreaming biodiversity, ecosystem services, including carbon sequestration, climate resilience and pollution reduction, and natural capital in the society and economy. Through education and NBS, the topic contributes to the transformative change necessary to tackle societal challenges, notably addressing the EU biodiversity strategy for 2030 and the EU climate adaptation strategy.
Duration	36 months
Application Deadlines	28/03/2023
Financial support type	Public funding. Public funding. Coordination and Support Action- Lump Sum Grant
Geographical coverage	Collaborative European coverage
Sectorial coverage	Agriculture, forestry, fisheries, Biodiversity
Type of Applicants	Research institutes, universities, academia, private companies
Link	Link

Name	HORIZON EUROPE European partnership on accelerating farming systems transition – agroecology living labs and research infrastructures
Short description	HORIZON-CL6-2023-FARM2FORK-01-1 This partnership will contribute to the objectives and targets of the new common agricultural policy (CAP), and of the EU farm to fork strategy for a transition to fair, healthy, environmentally-friendly and more resilient food systems from primary production to consumption, and in particular pursuing the ambition to boost agroecology. Moreover, the Commission Communication ‘Safeguarding food security and reinforcing the resilience of food systems’[1] highlights innovation through agroecology as one of the tools that can mitigate pressure on input costs without hurting production capacity, leading to long-term progress in productivity. Agroecology is a dynamic and holistic approach that contributes positively to healthier ecosystems and biodiversity, including in soils.
Duration	36 months
Application Deadlines	12/04/2023
Financial support type	Public funding. HORIZON Programme Cofund Actions. Grant Budget-Based
Geographical coverage	Collaborative European coverage
Sectorial coverage	Agriculture, forestry, fisheries, Biodiversity
Type of Applicants	agroecology partners, funding agencies, research performing organisations, regions, local authorities, research infrastructures, living laboratories, farmers, advisors, industry, consumers,
Link	Link

Name	European Funds for Modern Economy (FENG)
Short description	<p>FENG.02.17 Development of the cluster offer for companies: The action is aimed at: strengthening the professionalization of the activities of coordinators of supra-regional growth clusters, aspiring to obtain the status of National Key Clusters, in particular to develop an innovative service offer for companies in the field of R&D&I, including support for the internationalization of the offer of supra-regional growth clusters at industry events</p> <p>FENG.02.18 Development of the OI offer for companies: As part of the measure, the support is intended for the development of the potential of single innovation centres with specific functional specializations accredited by the minister competent for economy or consortium innovation centres with specific thematic specializations (including Digital Innovation Hubs (DIH) - digital innovation centres and Green Innovation Hubs (GIH) - centres of green innovation).</p> <p>Action FENX.01.04 Waste management and circular economy Education and information activities of the society, in particular in the area of waste prevention and waste management activities in accordance with the hierarchy of waste management methods and in the field of circular economy.</p>
Duration	36 months
Application Deadlines	2nd semester 2023
Financial support type	Grants
Geographical coverage	Poland
Sectorial coverage	Digital Innovation Hubs (DIH) - digital innovation centres and Green Innovation Hubs (GIH)
Type of Applicants	companies, as well as research organizations and business support institutions.
Link	Link

Name	European Regional Development Fund
Short description	<p>CF.CP2.VI - Supporting the transition towards a circular and resource-efficient economy. Financial instrument for regional development and cohesion in the EU. Education and information activities of the society, in particular in the area of waste prevention and waste management activities in accordance with the hierarchy of waste management methods and in the field of circular economy.</p>
Duration	2021-2027 (7-year programming period)
Application Deadlines	Varies depending on specific calls
Financial support type	Grants, loans, and other financial instruments
Geographical coverage	Poland
Sectorial coverage	Various sectors including innovation, entrepreneurship, research, infrastructure, sustainable development, etc.
Type of Applicants	Public authorities, regional and local entities, research organizations, SMEs, NGOs, etc.
Link	https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/funding/erdf_en

Name	European shared management funds (2021-2027)
Short description	<p>BG05SFPR001-3.001 - Modernization of Vocational Education and Training</p> <p>The main objective of the procedure is to help adapt vocational education and training to labour market dynamics and to support the development of skills for the professions of the present and the future.</p> <p>The specific objectives of the procedure are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Modernising the needs against labour market dynamics by working together between schools and other VET providers, business and other institutions; - Enhancing the skills and competences of pedagogical vocational training specialists and students in the vocational education and training system in partnership with business; - Increasing the attractiveness of vocational education and training.
Duration	36 months
Application Deadlines	Ongoing calls
Financial support type	Public funding incentives at Bulgarian level
Geographical coverage	Bulgaria
Sectorial coverage	Education, Human Resources, Competitiveness and Innovation, Environment
Type of Applicants	The main aim of the operation is: Encouraging and developing the potential for personal development of students for their permanent inclusion in school education and improving their educational results.
Link	https://eumis2020.government.bg/en/s/8d3ebf57-ff75-4ad5-afa1-5747f558ee98/Procedure/Active

Name	Erasmus+
Short description	<p>Key Action 2: Cooperation among organisations and institutions</p> <p>EU programme for education, training, youth and sport.</p> <p>Funding program supporting cooperation and innovation in education, training, and youth. The Erasmus+ program supports various actions, including partnerships for cooperation, partnerships for excellence, partnerships for innovation, capacity building projects, and not-for-profit European sport events. The program aims to contribute to the development, transfer, and implementation of innovative practices at various levels. It focuses on promoting excellence, mobility, intercultural understanding, inclusion, and the acquisition of skills and competences.</p>
Duration	Varies depending on specific actions and projects
Application Deadlines	Varies depending on specific calls and actions
Financial support type	Grants and funding for projects and activities
Geographical coverage	European Union member states and partner countries
Sectorial coverage	Education, training, youth, and sport
Type of Applicants	Educational institutions, youth organizations, vocational training providers, universities, NGOs, etc.
Link	https://erasmus-plus.ec.europa.eu/programme-guide/part-b/key-action-2

Irish BBEC

Public funding mechanisms in Ireland: In Ireland government agencies announce grant schemes/calls to action to apply for funding for relevant schemes. There are no such funding schemes currently open however the following list shows those most likely to have calls in the future and therefore be of interest to the BIObec Ireland Project.

Name	Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine (DAFM)
Short description	DAFM is the department of the government whose remit is to lead the sustainable development of the agri-food, forestry and marine sector and to optimise its contribution to national economic development and the natural environment. A direct responsibility for the bioeconomy is envisaged, as well as a potential source of grant funding for the Irish BBEC.
Duration	Varies depending on specific actions and projects
Application Deadlines	Varies depending on specific calls and actions
Financial support type	Grants
Geographical coverage	Ireland
Sectorial coverage	Agriculture, Food and the Marine
Type of Applicants	Educational institutions, Forestry agencies, Agri-food organisations.
Link	https://www.gov.ie/en/organisation/departments-of-agriculture-food-and-the-marine/

Name	Department of the Environment, Climate and Communications (DECC)
Short description	DECC is the department of the government responsible for the delivery of policies and programmes in a number of areas related to environment, climate and communications. There is a direct responsibility for climate and environmental issues, a potential source of grant funding for the Irish BBEC.
Duration	Varies depending on specific actions and projects
Application Deadlines	Varies depending on specific calls and actions
Financial support type	Grants
Geographical coverage	Ireland
Sectorial coverage	Environment, Climate and Communications
Type of Applicants	Educational institutions, Public Sector Climate-Action institutions, Youth agencies.
Link	https://www.gov.ie/en/organisation/departments-of-the-environment-climate-and-communications/

Name	Enterprise Ireland
Short description	Enterprise Ireland is the state agency responsible for supporting the development of manufacturing and internationally traded services companies. We provide funding and supports for companies - from entrepreneurs with business propositions for a high potential start-up through to large companies expanding their activities, improving efficiency and growing international sales. They also provide funding and supports for college based researchers to assist in the development, protection and transfer of technologies into industry via licensing or spin-out companies.
Duration	Varies depending on specific actions and projects
Application Deadlines	Varies depending on specific calls and actions
Financial support type	Grants , other funding sources
Geographical coverage	Ireland

Sectorial coverage	Green Transition Funds and Digital Transition Funds
Type of Applicants	Entrepreneurs with business propositions for a high potential start-up through to large companies to expand their businesses.
Link	https://www.enterprise-ireland.com/en/

Name	Science Foundation Ireland
Short description	Science Foundation Ireland(SFI) is the largest funder of competitive research in Ireland, focusing on science, technology, engineering & maths and their positive effect in the economic growth by driving a sustainable international economy.
Duration	Varies depending on specific actions and projects
Application Deadlines	Varies depending on specific calls and actions
Financial support type	Public funding calls
Geographical coverage	Ireland
Sectorial coverage	Educational programmes in Health, Bioeconomy, Climate and AI research
Type of Applicants	Researchers, food producers and industry stakeholders.
Link	https://www.sfi.ie/

Name	Higher Education Authority (HEA)
Short description	The Higher Education Authority (HEA) is the statutory agency responsible for the allocation of exchequer funding to the universities, institutes of technology (IoTs) and other higher education institutions (HEIs). The HEA leads the strategic development of the Irish higher education and research system with the objective of creating a coherent system of diverse institutions with distinct missions, which is responsive to the social, cultural and economic development of Ireland and its people and supports the achievement of national objectives.
Duration	Varies depending on specific actions and projects
Application Deadlines	Varies depending on specific calls and actions
Financial support type	Public funding calls and grants
Geographical coverage	Ireland
Sectorial coverage	Universities, Institutes of Technology and other Higher Education Institutions
Type of Applicants	Direct source of funding for higher education institutions through operational cost funding and building programmes
Link	https://hea.ie/funding-governance-performance/funding/

Name	Skillnet
Short description	Skillnet is a business support group of the Irish government. They partner with industry to create upskilling programmes which are responsive to business needs and designed to develop future ready talent. We believe that maintaining a highly skilled workforce is essential to our national competitiveness. Our business is to ensure that your business has the skills it needs to thrive. We currently support over 22,500 businesses nationwide and provide a wide range of valuable learning experiences to over 86,500 trainees. Our mission is to facilitate increased participation in enterprise training and workforce learning in Ireland.
Duration	Varies depending on specific actions and projects
Application Deadlines	Varies depending on specific calls and actions
Financial support type	Training programmes
Geographical coverage	Ireland
Sectorial coverage	Universities, Institutes of Technology and other Higher Education Institutions
Type of Applicants	Skillnet allocates funding to Skillnet Business Networks, which are groups of businesses within the same industry sector or region with similar training needs, so they can receive subsidised training.

Link	https://www.skillnetireland.ie/
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Name	Springboard+
Short description	Springboard+ is managed by the Higher Education Authority in Ireland and provides upskilling and reskilling courses to develop the talent base in key areas of the economy. Education providers apply to be recognised as a Springboard+ funded programme.
Duration	Varies depending on the course
Application Deadlines	Varies depending on the course
Financial support type	Free courses at certificate, degree and masters level
Geographical coverage	Ireland
Sectorial coverage	Key growth sectors of the economy
Type of Applicants	Unemployed or previously self-employed individuals, returners to the workforce, and those in employment who wish to upskill or reskill
Link	Springboard Skills and Engagement Higher Education Authority (hea.ie)

Name	SOLAS
Short description	SOLAS is the national agency responsible for funding, planning and co-ordinating Further Education and Training (FET) in Ireland. SOLAS works with Education and Training Boards (ETBs), Regional Skills Fora and local enterprises across Ireland to develop FET programmes that are responsive to the rapidly evolving skills, social and economic landscape unique to each region. SOLAS offers a range of programmes that are designed to meet the needs of learners at all levels. These programmes include apprenticeships, traineeships, community education programmes, adult literacy and numeracy programmes, and vocational training programmes. SOLAS also provides funding for research and development in the FET sector.
Duration	Varies depending on the course
Application Deadlines	Varies depending on the course
Financial support type	Free courses at certificate, degree and masters level
Geographical coverage	Ireland
Sectorial coverage	Agriculture, business, construction, engineering, healthcare, ICT, manufacturing and retail
Type of Applicants	Education and Training Boards (ETBs), Regional Skills Fora and local enterprises
Link	Solus Learning Works

Finnish BBEC

Name	Business Joensuu
Short description	Business Joensuu is a regional development company that promotes business growth and internationalization in the Joensuu region. Grow your business or start your own company in the Joensuu and Central Karelia region, you can get information, support and know-how.
Duration	Varies depending on the course
Application Deadlines	Varies depending on the course
Financial support type	Funding for start-up companies
Geographical coverage	Joensuu and Central Karelia region (Finland)
Sectorial coverage	Internationalization, investment, growing and scale-up services
Type of Applicants	Scale-ups and start-ups
Link	https://businessjoensuu.fi/

Name	Regional Council of North Karelia
Short description	The Regional Council of North Karelia is responsible for regional planning and general coordination of regional development programs related to national and EU structural funds.
Duration	NA
Application Deadlines	NA
Financial support type	Grants – Structural funding
Geographical coverage	North Karelia
Sectorial coverage	Internationalization, investment, growing and scale-up services
Type of Applicants	Scale-ups and start-ups - Individuals and organisations.
Link	https://pohjois-karjala.fi/home/

Name	ELY-centre
Short description	The aim of the ELY Centres is to ensure that adult education supports the participation of ordinary citizens in civic activities and working life. ELY Centres help to strengthen regional co-operation and networking in adult education between providers of education, companies and other stakeholders.
Duration	NA
Application Deadlines	NA
Financial support type	Grants – Regional development
Geographical coverage	Finland
Sectorial coverage	Business and industry, labour force, competence and cultural activities
Type of Applicants	Scale-ups and start-ups - Individuals and organisations.
Link	https://www.ely-keskus.fi/web/ely-en

Name	Business Finland
Short description	Business Finland offers funding for research, product development, and many kinds of business development needs, especially for small and medium-sized companies. Business Finland builds Finnish companies into success stories worthy of market celebrations. Our customers are companies seeking bold business renewal and growth in the international market.
Duration	NA
Application Deadlines	NA
Financial support type	Grants – Regional development
Geographical coverage	Finland
Sectorial coverage	Business and industry, labour force, competence and cultural activities
Type of Applicants	Scale-ups and start-ups - Individuals and organisations.
Link	Business Finland

Danish BBEC

Name	Viborg Municipality/ Business Viborg/Viborg Innovation Fund
Short description	The foundation's vision is to contribute to the development of Viborg Municipality culturally, socially and professionally, so that the municipality is seen as attractive for settlement and business establishment. Campus Viborg at Aarhus University is being developed. A BioBEC could add more to this. One of the key partners in forming the BioBEC, focus is local business development and jobs within bioeconomy
Duration	NA
Application Deadlines	NA
Financial support type	Donation To be defined. Can probably give a donation with KPIs for starting up the BioBEC (1-3 years funding)
Geographical coverage	Municipal / Regional (Viborg – Denmark)
Sectorial coverage	Cultura, social and business-oriented activities.
Type of Applicants	Regional partners focusing on boosting innovative projects in the Viborg municipality.
Link	https://www.viborginnovationfond.dk/

Name	Central Denmark Region
Short description	Central Jutland Region administers the Education Pool of DKK 20 million. DKK, which can be applied for by educational institutions. Two pools are available : the theme pool and the open pool. 80 percent of the annual funds in the Education pool are allocated to the theme pool, while 20 percent are allocated to the open pool. The pool supports two or three larger and longer-term projects with a broad partnership. There are three themes that can be searched under. In 2023, the themes are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More with the skills for the green transition • More with a skilled education • Improvement of basic skills .
Duration	NA
Application Deadlines	NA
Financial support type	Private funding advisory and grants
Geographical coverage	Municipal / Regional (Central Jutland Region)
Sectorial coverage	Education
Type of Applicants	Educational institutions that offer general and vocational youth education as well as general adult education.
Link	https://www.ru.rm.dk/uddannelse/uddannelsespulje

Name	Novo Nordic Foundation
Short description	Project support for science education and informal learning environments – 2023. The Novo Nordisk Foundation wants to promote natural science education and strengthen interest, knowledge and skills in natural science, technology and sustainability among children, young people and the population in Denmark in general.
Duration	NA
Application Deadlines	NA
Financial support type	Private funding – Venture Capital Up to DKK 6 million per grant
Geographical coverage	National - Denmark
Sectorial coverage	Education
Type of Applicants	Educational institutions focusing on Natural sciences – new informal educations/didactics
Link	https://novonordiskfonden.dk/grant/projektstoette-til-naturvidenskabelig-uddannelse-og-uformelle-laeringsmiljoer-2023/

Name	Anders Brøndums Velgørende Fund
Short description	Anders Brøndum's Charitable Foundation's primary purpose is to provide support for the beautification of areas and buildings and for cultural and sports facilities - all in Viborg Municipality. The foundation's primary purpose is to provide support for the beautification of areas and buildings and for cultural and sports facilities, all in Viborg municipality. The foundation also aims to provide support to individuals or organisations, including scientists, who work for a better environment in Viborg municipality.
Duration	NA
Application Deadlines	NA
Financial support type	Private funding – Venture Capital
Geographical coverage	Local
Sectorial coverage	Education
Type of Applicants	Educational institutions focusing on a “better environment in Viborg”
Link	https://www.ab-velgfond.dk/

German BBEC

Name	Ideenwettbewerb Bioökonomie 2023
Short description	Support innovative ideas and projects in the field of bioeconomy. It provides financial support to startups, SMEs, and research institutions to develop and implement their bioeconomy-related concepts. The program encourages the development of sustainable solutions and the creation of new value chains in the bioeconomy sector. The Ideenwettbewerb Bioökonomie 2023 is an innovation competition that seeks to promote outstanding marketable bioeconomic innovations in Baden-Württemberg. The competition is aimed at actors who have developed such innovations that make a verifiable contribution to the state's sustainable bioeconomy strategy.
Duration	All 2023
Application Deadlines	31/08/2023
Financial support type	Grant - Up to €100,000 in funding for each project
Geographical coverage	Regional - Baden-Württemberg
Sectorial coverage	Bioeconomy innovation and project development
Type of Applicants	Companies, start-ups, research institutions, universities and other organizations based in Baden-Württemberg
Link	Ideenwettbewerb Bioökonomie 2023

Name	Spitze auf den Land!. Technologieführer (ELR)
Short description	"Excellence in the Countryside", supports technological leaders in rural areas. It provides financial assistance to businesses and organizations in rural regions to develop and implement innovative projects. The program aims to strengthen the economic potential of rural areas, including the bioeconomy sector.
Duration	Not specified
Application Deadlines	28/02/2023
Financial support type	Grant
Geographical coverage	Regional - Baden-Württemberg
Sectorial coverage	Technological leadership and rural development
Type of Applicants	Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) based in rural areas of Baden-Württemberg
Link	Spitze auf den Land!. Technologieführer (ELR)

Name	Bioökonomie Innovations- und Investitionsprogram für den Ländlichen Raum
Short description	Promoting innovation and investment in the bioeconomy sector in rural areas. It supports projects that contribute to the sustainable use of biomass, the development of bio-based products and technologies, and the creation of jobs and economic growth in rural regions. The Bioeconomy Competition 2023 is an idea competition aimed at promoting marketable bioeconomic innovations that contribute to the development of Baden-Württemberg's bioeconomy. The competition is designed to support innovative projects that contribute to the development of the state's bioeconomy.
Duration	Not specified
Application Deadlines	15/09/2023
Financial support type	Grant – Up to 1M€
Geographical coverage	Regional - Baden-Württemberg
Sectorial coverage	Bioeconomy projects in rural areas
Type of Applicants	Bioeconomic approaches along the agricultural and forestry value chain agents
Link	Bioökonomie Innovations- und Investitionsprogram für den Ländlichen Raum

Name	Netzwerkinitiativen zur Weiterentwicklung der Leitregion Nachhaltige Bioökonomie
Short description	Support network initiatives for the advancement of sustainable bioeconomy in specific regions. It provides financial support to collaborative projects that bring together stakeholders from academia, industry, and government to promote knowledge exchange, innovation, and the development of bio-based value chains.
Duration	Not specified
Application Deadlines	04/10/2022
Financial support type	Grant
Geographical coverage	Regional - Baden-Württemberg
Sectorial coverage	Bioeconomy projects in rural areas
Type of Applicants	Network initiatives involving stakeholders from industry, research and society
Link	Netzwerkinitiativen zur Weiterentwicklung der Leitregion Nachhaltige Bioökonomie

Name	Struktur- und Innovationsfonds für die Forschung (SI-BW)
Short description	Provides funding to research institutions, universities, and companies for projects that contribute to regional economic development and competitiveness. The program covers various sectors, including the bioeconomy.
Duration	Not specified
Application Deadlines	Not specified
Financial support type	Grant
Geographical coverage	Regional - Baden-Württemberg
Sectorial coverage	Research and innovation projects in Baden-Württemberg
Type of Applicants	Universities, Research Institutions and companies based in BW.
Link	Struktur- und Innovationsfonds für die Forschung (SI-BW)

Name	InnovationChallenge – Nachhaltige Produktion und Mobilität
Short description	Promote sustainable production and mobility solutions. It supports innovative projects that contribute to the development and implementation of sustainable technologies, processes, and products in the bioeconomy and other related sectors.
Duration	Not specified
Application Deadlines	Several during 2023
Financial support type	Grant
Geographical coverage	Regional - Baden-Württemberg
Sectorial coverage	Sustainable production and mobility solutions in Baden-Württemberg
Type of Applicants	Universities, research institutions, and companies based in Baden-Württemberg
Link	InnovationChallenge – Nachhaltige Produktion und Mobilität

Name	Margarete von Wrangell-Programm
Short description	It focuses on supporting female researchers in their scientific careers. It provides funding for professorships and research projects led by women in areas such as bioeconomy and other scientific disciplines.
Duration	Not specified
Application Deadlines	Not specified
Financial support type	Grant – Careers in science and research
Geographical coverage	Baden-Württemberg
Sectorial coverage	Support for female researchers in scientific careers
Type of Applicants	Junior female researchers who have completed their doctorate and have already gained experience in research and teaching

Link	Margarete von Wrangell-Programm
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Name	Mathilde-Planck-Lehrauftragsprogramm
Short description	Supports teaching assignments and professorships at universities. It aims to promote the development and implementation of innovative teaching concepts, including in the field of bioeconomy. The Mathilde Planck Lehrbeauftragtenprogramm is a funding program that aims to increase the number of female professors in Baden-Württemberg by awarding more teaching assignments to female academics. The program is designed to provide female academics with the opportunity to gain pedagogical experience and establish connections with universities by taking on teaching assignments. The program is open to all disciplines and is aimed at women who have completed their doctorate and have already gained experience in research and teaching
Duration	NA
Application Deadlines	NA
Financial support type	Grant
Geographical coverage	Baden-Württemberg
Sectorial coverage	Innovative teaching concepts and professorships – Science and research
Type of Applicants	Female academics
Link	Mathilde-Planck-Lehrauftragsprogramm

Name	MuT-Mentoring und Training
Short description	Supporting female researchers in their career development. It provides mentoring, training, and networking opportunities to help women advance in their academic careers, including in the bioeconomy sector. Supporting female researchers in their career development. It provides mentoring, training, and networking opportunities to help women advance in their academic careers, including in the bioeconomy sector.
Duration	NA
Application Deadlines	NA
Financial support type	Funding
Geographical coverage	Baden-Württemberg
Sectorial coverage	Support for female researchers in career development
Type of Applicants	Female academics who have completed their doctorate and have already gained experience in research and teaching
Link	MuT-Mentoring und Training

Name	The research funding of the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF)
Short description	All tenders at a glance -As part of the National Bioeconomy Strategy, a total of six federal ministries support the development of a bio-based economy in Germany. There are also numerous funding measures at European level that are relevant to the bioeconomy. In addition, the federal states offer research funding.
Duration	Not specified
Application Deadlines	Available on the website
Financial support type	Grant
Geographical coverage	National – Germany
Sectorial coverage	R&D projects in the German Bioeconomy industry
Type of Applicants	Academia, Research institutes or SMEs/large companies
Link	BMBF

Name	Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture
Short description	One of the German Federal Government's aims is to strengthen rural regions as independent areas to live and work in, and to make them sustainable, future-proof and attractive, taking into account their different potential for development.
Duration	Not specified
Application Deadlines	Ongoing calls
Financial support type	Grant
Geographical coverage	National - Germany
Sectorial coverage	R&D projects in the German Food and agriculture industry
Type of Applicants	R&D companies
Link	Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture

Name	Nationale-stadtentwicklungspolitik
Short description	Integrated urban development begins with us: The National Urban Development Policy has been the driving force behind integrated urban development in Germany since 2007. We are a joint initiative of the federal, state and local governments.
Duration	Not specified
Application Deadlines	Ongoing challenges
Financial support type	Challenges support
Geographical coverage	National - Germany
Sectorial coverage	Urban Development challenges
Type of Applicants	Municipalities, public bodies or other urban development entities
Link	Nationale-stadtentwicklungspolitik

